

Research article

Moth flies (Diptera: Psychodidae) of Abkhazia (western Caucasus, Georgia) with some additional faunistic data from Armenia, Georgia, and Russia

Jan Ježek¹, Jozef Oboňa², Peter Manko³

- (1) Department of Entomology, National Museum, Cirkusová 1740, CZ – 193 00 Prague 9 – Horní Počernice, Czech Republic, jan.jezek@o2active.cz
- (2) [Corresponding author] Department of Ecology, Faculty of Humanities and Natural Sciences, University of Prešov, 17. novembra 1, SK – 081 16 Prešov, Slovakia, jozef.obona@unipo.sk
- (3) Department of Ecology, Faculty of Humanities and Natural Sciences, University of Prešov, 17. novembra 1, SK – 081 16 Prešov, Slovakia, peter.manko@unipo.sk

Abstract: This paper attempts to fill the knowledge gaps in biodiversity of non-biting moth flies in the Caucasus (especially in Abkhazia) and create a suitable basis for subsequent (not only) ecological studies. In total, records of 65 Psychodidae (Sycoracinae – one sp., Psychodinae 64 spp., altogether 33 genera) species/subspecies are presented based on specimens collected mainly in Abkhazia, with some additional data from Armenia, Georgia, and Russia (12 new records). The Psychodidae fauna of Abkhazia now comprises 57 species, 31 of which are newly listed here. The Caucasus region (including the territory of Abkhazia presented here) should be considered the most biologically rich and most endangered region in the world, with an exceptional richness of endemic and endangered species also from the point of view of psychodids biodiversity. Sixteen extremely rare species in this family (probably Caucasus or highland endemics) which need to be given increased attention, whether from the point of view of island ecology or biodiversity protection, have been herein confirmed.

Keywords: Abkhazia, biodiversity, checklist, distribution, faunistics, moth flies, new records, Palaearctic Region, Transcaucasia, western great Caucasus, zoogeography

Introduction

Taxonomy is an essential tool for understanding biodiversity. It is also essential in biodiversity conservation and in addressing many critical and current nature conservation issues (e.g. McNeely, 2002; Kociolek & Stoermer, 2001; Schlick-Steiner et al., 2010). Therefore, much recent research in ecology and biodiversity conservation has been based mainly on taxonomic and faunal works. However, the availability of these data varies considerably from a spatial, temporal, and often taxonomic point of view. This creates gaps in biodiversity information (Amano et al., 2016). Particularly large gaps in biodiversity research can be observed in the Caucasus countries (Wetzel et al., 2018), and Diptera, specifically the family Psychodidae, are a good example of this (see

Oboňa et al. (2017, 2019a, b); Ježek et al. (2018, 2021a) and supplemented checklist here. In particular, the low intensity of research is the reason why part of the entomofauna of the Caucasus is still unknown.

Many papers have presented the characteristics of Caucasian mountains of Abkhazia; they are listed, e. g., in the book *Priroda Abchazii (The Nature of Abkhazia)* – Kufyreva et al. (1961). Some important entomological papers (Diptera: Psychodidae) concerning the countries of Transcaucasia have been published in the last several decades: Wagner (1981, 1990); Vaillant & Joost (1983); Oboňa et al. (2017, 2019a, b); Ježek et al. (2018, 2021a) as well as some added accounts with non-western Caucasian species included, incl. neighbouring countries – Ježek (1992a, 1995b, 1999). However, the Psychodidae of Abkhazia are still rather poorly known. In particular, data on non-phlebotomine

moth flies have been scattered in various papers and never summarised. New faunistic records and new taxa from the Abkhazian mountains (Western Caucasus) and their foothills were reported in following papers: *Parajungiella abchazica* Ježek, 1985 in Ježek (1985); *Yomormia achalshenica* Ježek, 1987, *Y. afonensis* Ježek, 1987, *Y. furva* (Tonnoir, 1940) and *Mormia ckvitariorum* Ježek, 1987 in Ježek (1987); *Seoda svanetica* (Ježek, 1989) in Ježek (1989); *Psychodocha cinerea* (Banks, 1894), *P. gemina* (Eaton, 1904) and *Psychodula minuta* (Banks, 1894) in Ježek (1990a); *Paramormia (P.) polyascoidea* (Krek, 1971) in Ježek (1990b); *Sycorax caucasica* Ježek, 1990 in Ježek (1990c); *Philosepedon clouense* Ježek, 1994 in Ježek (1994); *Kvazbamormia pskhuensis* Ježek, 1995 in Ježek (1995a); *Threticus petrosus* Ježek, 1997 and *Tonnoiriella arcuata* Ježek, 1997 in Ježek (1997); *Szaboiella hibernica* (Tonnoir, 1940) in Ježek (2004a); *Lepimormia georgica* (Wagner, 1981), *Peripsychoda auriculata* (Haliday in Curtis, 1839), *Philosepedon (Trichosepedon) balkanicum* Krek, 1971, *Threticus balkaneoalpinus* Krek, 1972, *T. negrobovi* Vaillant, 1972, *Chodopsycha lobata* (Tonnoir, 1940), *Logima erminea* (Eaton, 1893), *Pericoma (Pachypericoma) blandula* Eaton, 1893, *P. (P.) fallax* Eaton, 1893 and *Pneumia g. gracilis* (Eaton, 1893) in Ježek (2004b – *balkaneoalpinus* as well in 1995c); *Pneumia nubila* (Meigen, 1818) and *P. palustris* (Meigen, 1804) in Ježek & Hájek (2007, erratum).

As it is very important to fill these knowledge gaps, the presented research is devoted to expanding knowledge (filling the knowledge gap) of the biodiversity of non-biting Psychodidae of the Caucasus (especially from Abkhazia), thus creating a suitable basis for subsequent, not only ecological, studies.

Material and methods

Moth flies (for concise characteristics and biology, see e.g. Ježek et al., 2019, 2021b) were collected by the first author in Abkhazia (Fig. 1) the summer seasons of 1983, 1985 and 1988 by sweep-netting from vegetation growing in swamps, source areas and along watercourses and water reservoirs, alpine and subalpine habitats, as well as lowland biotopes. P. Chvojka, J. Dlabola and J. Šumpich (National Museum, Prague, Department of Entomology) provided extensive additional material from Georgia, Russia and Armenia.

The captured specimens were preserved in 75% ethanol in the field, and the Psychodidae specimens (cleared in chlorophenol, treated in xylol, and mounted on glass slides in Canada balsam) were identified by J. Ježek in a laboratory and deposited at the National Museum (Natural History Museum), Department of Entomology, Prague, Czech Republic. The slides are numbered with two separate series of numbers: INS = Inventory Slide Number of the family Psychodidae, and Cat. No. = Catalogue Numbers of slides of types and historical specimens of Diptera and are included in the Diptera collection (National Museum Prague collections – NMPC, see Tkoč et al., 2014).

Identification keys used: Vaillant (1971–1983); Szabó (1983); Withers (1989) and numerous unnamed original papers by different authors with descriptions of new species. The nomenclature is modified from Vaillant (1971–1983) and Wagner (1990, 2019) using the classifications of e.g. Ježek & van Harten (2005, 2009); Ježek (2007); Krek (1999); Omelková & Ježek (2012); Oboňa & Ježek (2014); Kvitte (2014); Kroča & Ježek (2019) and Ježek et al. (2019, 2021a).

The List of localities section contains the following data: transcript of the site name from the site label, locality number (in parentheses), the currently used site name (if available) and country, more detailed characteristics of the collection habitat, approximate collection coordinates (found according to site descriptions), approximate altitude, habitat vegetation inventory (if available).

The Unpublished records section contains the following data: country, transcript of the site name from the site label, locality number (in parentheses), the number and sex of the samples examined, date, collector's name and collection method (if available) and slides numbers.

The map presented in Fig. 1 is prepared using QGIS software (version: 3.10.10-A Coruña), data derived from the USGS/NASA SRTM providing seamless continuous topography surfaces (Jarvis et al., 2008), and from Natural Earth (free vector and raster map data @ [naturalearthdata.com](https://www.naturalearthdata.com)).

List of localities

(recorded species are summarised in Table 1)

- 1 Achalsopeli (Akhalsopeli – Georgia (Abkhazia)), wet small meadow, 43°00'N 41°06'E, 140 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Alisma*, *Scirpus*, *Carex*, *Mentha*.

Fig. 1. Maps of sampling sites in Abkhazia (larger map with coloured elevation) and outside Abkhazia (a map showing the boundaries and shaded sampling area in Abkhazia).

- 2 Achalseni (Akhalseni – Georgia (Abkhazia)), village env. Sukhumi, farms, wet road banks, rocks, swamps near crossways, 43°07'N 41°01'E, 490 m a.s.l., veg.: *Acer*, *Alnus*, *Corylus*, *Rubus*, *Hedera*, *Fragaria*, Marchantiopsida, Musci.
- 3 Achalseni near Sroma (Akhalseni near Shroma – Georgia (Abkhazia)), Sukhumi environs, Vostočnaja Gumista River, rilllets near a stone crusher, 43°05'N 41°01'E, 200 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Sambucus*, *Rubus*.
- 4 Acigvara (Achigvara – Georgia (Abkhazia)), Gali environs, muddy brook in tea plantations, 42°41'N 41°38'E, 40 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Pteris*, *Polygonum*, *Rubus*, *Camellia*.
- 5 Adanga Pass (Adange – Georgia (Abkhazia)), a basin with swamps, small brook from the pass, big stones, 43°19'N 41°16'E, 2470 m a.s.l., veg.: *Fagus*, *Picea*, *Rhododendron*, *Petasites*, *Caltha*, *Scirpus*, *Rumex*, *Luzula*, *Orchis*, Pteropsida.
- 6 Adjaria (Georgia), Mtirala NP, Chakvistavi ca. 20 km NE of Batumi, left and right tributaries of Chakvistiskali River, brooks, streams, springs, 41°40'N 41°51'E, 250–410 m a.s.l., Chvojka leg.
- 7 Anaria (Anaria – Georgia (Abkhazia)), 7 km E of Ilori, spring area, 42°42'N 41°34'E, 30 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Sambucus*, *Robinia*, *Polygonum*, Marchantiopsida.
- 8 Areni (Armenia), Noravank monastery environs, rocky steppe, 39°41'N, 45°12'E, 1330 m a.s.l., Šumpich leg.
- 9 Azgara (Azhara – Georgia (Abkhazia)), environs of Levj Ptys, forest brook, wet road banks, Alnetum, muddy pasture near river, 43°06'N 41°42'E, 920 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Carpinus*, *Fagus*, *Picea*, *Corylus*, *Rubus*, *Fragaria*, *Leonurus*, *Juncus*, *Hieracium*, *Urtica*, *Impatiens*, *Valeriana*, *Petasites*, Musci, Pteropsida.

- 10 Azgara – Narzan (Azgara – Georgia (Abkhazia)), larger environs of Maruch Pass, wet bank or slope of a road near a river, Alnetum, marshes, tea plantations, montane stream, 43°06'N 41°42'E, 940 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Fagus*, *Picea*, *Eucalyptus*, *Rubus*, *Rumex*, *Inula*, *Scirpus*, *Caltha*, *Carex*, Pteropsida.
- 11 Baskacara (Georgia (Abkhazia)), Levyj Ptys environs, swamps, small forest brooks near river, Alnetum, streams below glaciers, 43°12'N 41°40'E, 3330 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Fagus*, *Picea*, *Rubus*, *Fragaria*, *Juncus*, *Scirpus*, *Trollium*, *Urtica*, *Lycopodium*, *Inula*, *Petasites*, Musci, Pteropsida.
- 12 Below Adanga Pass (Adange Pass – Georgia (Abkhazia)), 8 km from the pass, marches, small forest brook, Azgara River, clump of alders, slope, 43°19'N 41°16'E, 2470 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Fagus*, *Picea*, *Petasites*, *Scirpus*, *Luzula*, *Orchis*, *Rumex*, *Fragaria*, *Caltha*, Pteropsida.
- 13 Below Chimsa Pass – River Ubus (Ubusch R.– Georgia (Abkhazia)), small sources, 43°20'N 41°05'E, 1590 m a.s.l., veg.: *Rhododendron*, *Salix*, *Alchemilla*, Pteropsida.
- 14 Below Maruch Pass (Georgia (Abkhazia)), Levyj Ptys environs, spring areas, small brooks in Alnetum near river, high alder forest, fountain, marches, 43°10'N 41°43'E, 1150 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Fagus*, *Picea*, *Abies*, *Rubus*, *Petasites*, *Asperula*, *Rumex*, *Ranunculus*, *Urtica*, *Scirpus*, *Alisma*, Musci, Pteropsida.
- 15 Below Ulm Pass (Georgia (Abkhazia)), rills of marches, 43°20'N 40°42'E, 1880 m a.s.l., veg.: *Rhododendron*, *Salix*, *Alchemilla*, Pteropsida.
- 16 Beslachuba (Beslakhuba – Georgia (Abkhazia)), Ocamcira environs, large pools near road, swamps in the vicinity of a churchyard, 42°45'N 41°31'E, 55 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Populus*, *Sambucus*, *Rubus*, *Polygonum*, *Urtica*, Pteropsida.
- 17 Bzyb (Bzipi – Georgia (Abkhazia)), river 2–7 km from source area, Baskacara environs, small brooks in beech wood, sometimes with mineral water, marches, clump of alders, 43°13'N 40°22'E, 30 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Fagus*, *Picea*, *Rubus*, *Petasites*, *Rumex*, *Asperula*, *Oxalis*, *Ranunculus*, *Caltha*, Pteropsida.
- 18 Cebelda (Tsebelda – Georgia (Abkhazia)), arable land, fields, canals of irrigation, wet meadows, dried Alnetum, 43°01'N 41°16'E, 470 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Sambucus*, *Salix*, *Rubus*, *Scirpus*, *Typha*, *Fragaria*, *Pteris*, *Lythrum*, *Urtica*.
- 19 Chimsa near Ulm (Georgia (Abkhazia)), Bzybiskij Chrebet comb (Bzybiskij Khrebet), waterfalls, subalpine meadows in vicinity of passes, 43°20'N 40°43'E, 2300 m a.s.l., veg.: *Rhododendron*, *Alchemilla*, Pteropsida.
- 20 Cimuri (Georgia (Abkhazia)), larger environs of Sukhumi, Bzybiskij Chrebet comb (Bzybiskij Khrebet), glades, marches in Alnetum, hygropetric rocky walls, spring areas, rotten wood, Vostočnaja Gumista River, stream below a bridge, rocks, gate to NR, 43°05'N 41°00'E, 85 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Fagus*, *Carpinus*, *Juglans*, *Rhododendron*, *Sambucus*, *Hedera*, *Rumex*, *Juncus*, Pteropsida, Marchantiopsida, Musci.
- 21 Cimuri near Achalseni (nr. Akhalsheni – Georgia (Abkhazia)), Sukhumi district, pastures, sources almost without plants, 43°05'N 41°01'E, 150 m a.s.l., veg.: *Fagus*, *Fragaria*.
- 22 Cchalta (Chkhalta – Georgia (Abkhazia)), marches near river, spring areas, 43°05'N 41°39'E, 720 m a.s.l., veg.: *Juglans*, *Alnus*, *Sambucus*, *Geranium*, *Polygonum*, *Leonurus*, *Urtica*, *Persicaria*, Marchantiopsida.
- 23 Clou – Kodorskij Chrebet comb (Kodorskij Khrebet – Georgia (Abkhazia)), gorge, brook, hygropetric rocky walls, 42°58'N 41°51'E, 2330 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Rhododendron*, *Rosa*, *Rubus*, *Petasites*, *Hepatica*, *Phyllitis*, *Urtica*, *Inula*, Pteropsida, Marchantiopsida, Musci.
- 24 Cerna Voda (Georgia (Abkhazia)), Baskacara environs, river, small brooks with flocculated Fe, marches, beech wood, 43°12'N 41°40'E, 3430 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Fagus*, *Picea*, *Rubus*, *Caltha*, *Petasites*, *Ranunculus*.
- 25 Dagomys (Dagomys – Krasnodar Krai, Russia), settlement, 13 km NW from Sochi, 43°40'N 39°40'E, 20 m a.s.l., Dlabola leg.
- 26 Dou Pass (Dou Pass – Georgia (Abkhazia)) – small brook, 43°17'N 40°52'E, 1390 m a.s.l., veg.: *Fagus*, *Rhododendron*, *Alnus*, *Juglans*, *Prunus*, *Urtica*, Pteropsida.
- 27 Dou near Bzyb (Dou Pass near Bzipi – Georgia (Abkhazia)), slope glade on the way from the pass to river, small brook, 43°20'N 40°50'E, 580 m a.s.l., veg.: *Fagus*, *Rhododendron*, *Alnus*, *Juglans*, *Prunus*, *Urtica*, Pteropsida.
- 28 Dvurecje near Dou (Georgia (Abkhazia)), slope habitat 1200–1350 m below pass, path course to Dou River, plant liana strings above water, Bryophyta of flow stones, glade with small brook

- and gamekeeper's lodge, fallen branches, hygropetric rocky walls, small streams, 43°16'N 40°54'E, 1100 m a.s.l., veg.: *Fagus*-forest, *Rhododendron*, *Alnus*, *Phyllitis*, *Asplenium*, *Alchemilla*, *Viola*, *Pteris*, Pteropsida, Musci.
- 29 Džgerda (Jgerda – Georgia (Abkhazia)), Kodorskij Chrebet comb, small forest brook, pastures, impervious fences, rills, fluvials, 42°54'N 41°21'E, 176 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Fraxinus*, *Fagus*, *Crataegus*, *Ilex*, *Rhododendron*, *Rubus*, *Hedera*, *Pteris*, Marchantiopsida.
- 30 Gagra (Gagra – Georgia (Abkhazia)), town spring areas, gardens, 43°16'N 40°16'E, 125 m a.s.l., veg.: *Salix*, *Ficus*, *Sambucus*, *Rubus*.
- 31 Gali (Gali – Georgia (Abkhazia)), rivulet, swamps, *Camellia* hedgerows, 42°37'N 41°44'E, 60 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Pteris*, *Polygonum*, *Scirpus*, *Camellia*.
- 32 Gencvici (Gentsvishi – Georgia (Abkhazia)), river, brook, swamps in Alnetum, paludal habitats, 43°06'N 41°48'E, 895 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Picea*, *Urtica*, *Polygonum*, Musci.
- 33 GES – Sukhumi (Georgia (Abkhazia)), district town environs, hydroelectric power station, monkey farm env. River Gumista nr. Achalseni (Akhalseni) (6 km from Sukhumi), branches of *Corylus* over footpath, 43°05'N 41°00'E, 90 m a.s.l., veg.: *Sambucus*, *Rhododendron*, *Urtica*.
- 34 Ilori (Ilori – Georgia (Abkhazia)), creek, turning from main flow to Pokveš (Pokvesh), marches in Alnetum, 42°41'N 41°29'E, 13 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Rubus*, *Polygonum*.
- 35 Imereli (Georgia), prov., Baghdati near Saime, Tsablarastskali River, 41°58' N, 42°47' E, 385 m a.s.l., Chvojka leg.
- 36 Juznyj Prijut Pass (Georgia (Abkhazia)), waterfalls, hygropetric rocky walls, 43°08'N 42°03'E, 1940 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Rhododendron*.
- 37 Kaldachvara (Kaldakhvara – Georgia (Abkhazia)), eastern border of the settlement, town Bzyb (Bzipi) region, tunnel below road, small brook in Alnetum, 43°13'N 40°25'E, 80 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Sambucus*, *Corylus*, *Hedera*, *Urtica*, *Rubus*, Pteropsida, Musci.
- 38 Kaldachvara near Mjusoera (Kaldakhvara near Myussera – Georgia (Abkhazia)), crossways, swamps in Alnetum, 43°13'N 40°26'E, 130 m a.s.l., veg.: *Typha*, *Alisma*, *Juncus*, *Mentha*.
- 39 Kaman (Kamani – Georgia (Abkhazia)), village env. Sukhumi, well in glade with small brook, white stones, 43°03'N 41°02'E, 230 m a.s.l., veg.: *Carpinus*, *Sambucus*, *Zea*, Pteropsida, Marchantiopsida, Musci.
- 40 Kelasuri (Kelasuri – Georgia (Abkhazia)), river and settlement env. Sukhumi, Kodorskij Chrebet comb (Kodorskij Khrebet), Alnetum, swamps near riverbed, small brook, pastures, clough, hygropetric rocky walls, 43°01'N 41°06'E, 200 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Carpinus*, *Rhododendron*, *Sambucus*, *Hedera*, *Rubus*, *Phyllitis*, *Petasites*, *Alisma*, *Impatiens*, Pteropsida, Marchantiopsida, Musci.
- 41 Kingdi – vicinity of Gulripši (Gulripshi – Georgia (Abkhazia)), Alnetum near road, marches, 42°55'N 41°05'E, 7 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Carpinus*, *Corylus*, *Sambucus*, *Scirpus*, *Hedera*, *Urtica*, Pteropsida, Musci.
- 42 Kochora (Kokhora – Georgia (Abkhazia)), 3 km NW of Gali, swamps in Alnetum near road, 42°40'N 41°44'E, 140 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Rhododendron*, *Rubus*, *Polygonum*.
- 43 Kot – Kot (Georgia (Abkhazia)), a pastoral community of grazing management approximately 2350 m a.s.l., Bzybiskij Chrebet comb (Bzybiskij Khrebet), nr. peak Khimsa (3033 m a.s.l.), 43°19'N 40°43'E, 1880 m a.s.l., veg.: *Hieracium*, *Alchemilla*, *Polygonum*, Pteropsida.
- 44 Kot – Kot near Cimuri (Georgia (Abkhazia)), a pastoral community in Bzybiskij Chrebet comb. (Bzybiskij Khrebet), Sukhumi distr., glade, forest zone, lakes, small brooks, pools, trickling rocky slopes, peat and swamp bogs, river, marches, beech wood, 43°18'N 40°42'E, 2070 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Acer*, *Picea*, *Sambucus*, *Carpinus*, *Robinia*, *Sorbus*, *Fagus*, *Rhododendron*, *Petasites*, *Caltha*, *Juncus*, *Scirpus*, *Impatiens*, *Rumex*, *Inula*, *Asperula*, *Hieracium*, *Alchemilla*, *Polygonum*, *Sphagnum*, *Lemna*, Pteropsida, Musci.
- 45 Kot – Kot near Ulm Pass (Georgia (Abkhazia)), Bzybiskij Chrebet (Bzybiskij Khrebet) comb behind Ulm Pass, pastoral community, glades, lakes, swamps, 43°17'N 40°39'E, 1000 m a.s.l., veg.: *Fagus*, *Alnus*, *Acer*, *Sorbus*, *Juncus*, *Rumex*, *Petasites*, *Caltha*, Pteropsida.
- 46 Kutol Kodorskij Chrebet comb (Kodorskij Khrebet – Georgia (Abkhazia)), village, small meadow, fountain, 42°56'N 41°51'E, 1300 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Polygonum*.
- 47 Lehvaz (Armenia), environs, 3 km NWW of Meghri, Arevik NP, rocky steppe, gorge, 38°54'N 46°13'E, 844 m a.s.l., Šumpich leg.

- 48 Levyj Ptyz (Georgia (Abkhazia)), spring area near river, fallen branches, trickling banks of road, brook, 43°12'N 41°40'E, 3430 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Fagus*, *Juglans*, *Corylus*, *Polygonum*, *Lythrum*, *Fragaria*, *Leonurus*, Pteropsida, Marchantiopsida, Musci.
- 49 Macara (Machara – Georgia (Abkhazia)), Sukhumi distr., mandarin garden plantation (day as well as night collecting), walled WC, river, irrigation canal, village rill, shallow stony riverbed, almost dried ditch in building site, 42°56'N 41°05'E, 10 m a.s.l., veg.: *Citrus*, *Pinus*, *Alnus*, *Populus*, *Prunus*, *Corylus*, *Rubus*, *Alisma*, *Mentha*, *Typha*, *Hedera*, *Urtica*.
- 50 Maruch near Adanga (Marukhi Pass Georgia (Abkhazia)), small brook near footpath in the vicinity of both passes, 43°20'N 41°22'E, 2140 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Acer*, *Corylus*, *Picea*, *Rumex*, *Petasites*.
- 51 Mercheuli (Merkheuli – Georgia (Abkhazia)), 8 km from Macara (bridge), Sukhumi district, houses, brook, marches, hills, hygropetric rocky wells, conglomerate rocks, 42°59'N 41°09'E, 60 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Rubus*, Pteropsida, Marchantiopsida, Musci.
- 52 Mramba – Cebelda (Tsebelda – Georgia (Abkhazia)), environs, sheer slope, pasture, well, muddy pools of domestic pigs, stream, branches of oak and hazel shrubs above water, 43°01'N 41°16'E, 450 m a.s.l., veg.: *Quercus*, *Corylus*, *Alnus*, *Pteris*, *Urtica*, *Mentha*.
- 53 Niznaja Zemo – Azara (Azhara – Georgia (Abkhazia)), marches near village, rubbish, crocks, 43°06'N 41°41'E, 560 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Polygonum*, *Leonurus*.
- 54 Novyj Afon near Anuchva (54) (Akhali Atoni – Georgia (Abkhazia)), Psyrcha River, riverbed, spring areas, fountain, small brooks, rocks, 43°06'N 40°47'E, 230 m a.s.l., veg.: *Sambucus*, *Carpinus*, *Ficus*, *Buxus*, *Rubus*, *Asplenium*, Marchantiopsida.
- 55 Ocamcira (Ochamchire – Georgia (Abkhazia)), refuse in ditches, 42°43'N 41°29'E, 10 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Carpinus*, *Rhododendron*, *Rubus*, *Polygonum*, *Urtica*, *Pteris*.
- 56 Okumi (Okumi – Georgia (Abkhazia)), 2–4 km SW of the village, Tkvarceli env., S of Kodorskiy Chrebet comb (Kodorskiy Khrebet), brook, pastures, marches, runnel in tenuous pine wood, 42°42'N 41°44'E, 170 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Pinus*, *Larix*, *Robinia*, *Rubus*, *Luzula*, *Carex*, *Polygonum*, *Pteris*, *Mentha*.
- 57 Otap (Otapi – Georgia (Abkhazia)), Kodorskiy Chrebet comb (Kodorskiy Khrebet), slope, pasture, wet places, branches of alders above stream, swamps near way and in hillside, brook, thorny fences, 42°55'N 41°32'E, 230 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Salix*, *Sambucus*, *Lythrum*, *Polygonum*.
- 58 Pskhu (nr. P'skhus Nakrdzali – Georgia (Abkhazia)), a beautiful green valley, alluvial zone and wet places on banks of the River Bzyb (Bzipi), (2.5 km from the settlement, approximately 1400 m a.s.l. – southern and northern border), marshes, swamps, pools, pastures, clearings, tenuous alder forest, shaded sources by different plants, small forest brooks, streams, rills, (trickling southern slopes incl. regional airport), farming residents 100 m from Bzyb (Bzipi) River, small meadows, fenced gardens, branches of alders above flows, 43°20'N 40°54'E, 1830 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Fagus*, *Juglans*, *Sambucus*, *Corylus*, *Rubus*, *Inula*, *Carex*, *Equisetum*, *Juncus*, *Mentha*, *Pteris*, *Hedera*, *Poaceae*, *Fragaria*, *Hepatica*, *Urtica*, *Impatiens*, *Plantago*, *Mentha*, *Alisma*, *Trollius*, *Lythrum*, Pteropsida, Musci, Marchantiopsida.
- 59 Pskhu near Dou (nr. P'skhus Nakrdzali near Dou Pass – Georgia (Abkhazia)), southern footpath from border of the village to Dou Pass, farming residents, small brooks, spring areas, 43°18'N 40°56'E 1900 m a.s.l., veg.: *Juglans*, *Corylus*, *Rubus*, *Inula*, *Impatiens*, *Urtica*, *Mentha*.
- 60 Reka near Gali – Ilori environs (Georgia (Abkhazia)), crossways, 42°41'N 41°29'E, 2 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Polygonum*.
- 61 Resava (Georgia (Abkhazia)) environs, ca. 1300 m below Dou Pass, swamps in beech forest, fallen tree branches, 43°17'N 40°52'E, 1390 m a.s.l., veg.: *Fagus*, *Alnus*, *Corylus*, *Juncus*, *Carex*, Pteropsida.
- 62 Rica (Georgia (Abkhazia)), larger Gagra environs, dried canal with wet places, road, small rocky brook, lake, 43°19'N 40°15'E, 120 m a.s.l., veg.: *Acer*, *Carpinus*, *Picea*, *Petasites*, *Inula*, *Asplenium*, *Urtica*, *Fragaria*, *Stachys*.
- 63 Sagra near Tamys (Tsagera near Tamishi – Georgia (Abkhazia)), road to Ocamcira (Sukhumi environs), arable land, fields, ditch in tea plantations, 42°47'N 41°23'E, 20 m a.s.l., veg.: *Eucalyptus*, *Alnus*, *Rubus*, *Juncus*, *Zea*, *Camellia*.
- 64 Saken (Sakeni – Georgia (Abkhazia)), 90 km from Sukhumi, river, small montane brooks with pools,

- swamps in alder forest, 43°05'N 41°53'E, 990 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Corylus*, *Geranium*, *Leonurus*, *Urtica*, Musci.
- 65 Saken – Narzan (nr. Sakeni – Georgia (Abkhazia)), montane chalets near peaks above settlement, spring areas, small brooks, river, lush alder growth, forest marches and swamps, pasture muddy sections, slopes, glade streams, tributaries of lakes, branches of alders above water flows, fallen tree branches, collecting as well in night (22:00), 43°04'N 41°53'E, 1170 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Fagus*, *Acer*, *Picea*, *Corylus*, *Juglans*, *Prunus*, *Sambucus*, *Rubus*, *Equisetum*, *Juncus*, *Impatiens*, *Fragaria*, *Inula*, *Ranunculus*, *Trollius*, *Petasites*, *Alchemilla*, *Myosotis*, *Aquilegia*, *Heracleum*, *Rumex*, *Geranium*, Pteropsida, Musci.
- 66 Saken near Juznyj Prijut Pass (Sakeni – Georgia (Abkhazia)), marches near road (crossways), small brook, Alnetum, 43°04'N 41°57'E, 1300 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Geranium*, *Leonurus*, *Urtica*.
- 67 Serbista (Georgia (Abkhazia)), larger environs of the Maruch Pass, alder forest, small brooks, muddy pasture, 43°10'N 41°42'E, 1410 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Petasites*, *Rumex*, *Caltha*, *Inula*.
- 68 Shvanidzor (Armenia), environs, Arevik NP, rocky steppe, 38°56'N 46°22'E, 780 m a.s.l., Šumpich leg.
- 69 Svanetia (Georgia), SE, N and W of Mestia, left brook (stream) tributary of Mulkhura River, and Dolra River (left tributary of) above Ushkhvan, source area, 43°02'N 42°46'E, 1370–1700 m a.s.l., Chvojka leg.
- 70 Sroma (Shroma – Georgia (Abkhazia)), Sukhumi distr., hills, sources near stone crusher, 43°04'N 41°01'E, 240 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Robinia*, *Rubus*, *Juncus*, *Mentha*.
- 71 Tamys (Tamishi – Georgia (Abkhazia)), vicinity of Sukhumi, alder growth near road, brook, swamps, tea plantations, 42°47'N 41°22'E, 15 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Eucalyptus*, *Rubus*, *Scirpus*, *Caltha*, *Camellia*.
- 72 Tkvarceli (Tkvarcheli – Georgia (Abkhazia)), 3 km E of the settlement, stream near Galidzga (Ghalidzga) river, limestone areas, branches of alders above water, 42°51'N 41°38'E, 160 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Buxus*.
- 73 Ubus (Ubusch – Georgia (Abkhazia)), river as tributary of Bzyb (Bzipi) flow (in a distance 3–5 km), wet slopes and small brooks in beech wood, pasture, glade, grazing banks, 43°20'N 41°06'E, 1390 m a.s.l., veg.: *Fagus*, *Alnus*, *Picea*, *Petasites*, *Rumex*, *Inula*, *Caltha*, Pteropsida.
- 74 Ubus near Bzyb (Ubusch near Bzipi – Georgia (Abkhazia)), confluence of rivers, clearings in riverbed, 43°21'N 41°06'E, 1340 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Heracleum*, *Caltha*.
- 75 Vedi (Armenia), Goravan village environs, Goravan sands, Sanctuary sandy steppe, 39°53'N 44°43'E, 956 m a.s.l., Šumpich leg.
- 76 Yerevan (Armenia), 13 km SE of the town, Hatsavan nr. Azat Reservoir, steppe, 40°06'N 44°50'E, 1071 m a.s.l., Šumpich leg.
- 77 Zemo – Azara (Kvemo Azhara – Georgia (Abkhazia)), swamps in Alnetum near river, brook, stream, small flows, spring area, branches of alders above flows, grazing banks, swamps, old pots, 43°06'N 41°42'E, 540 m a.s.l., veg.: *Alnus*, *Sambucus*, *Rhododendron*, *Corylus*, *Buxus*, *Rubus*, *Fragaria*, *Leonurus*, *Geranium*, *Polygonum*, *Urtica*, Marchantiopsida, Musci.

Results

List of species

Sycorax caucasica Ježek, 1990 – Published records: Ježek (1990c): Azgara (9), Južnj Prijut Pass (36), Levyj Ptys (48), Mercheuli (51), Saken (64), Saken – Narzan (65), Serbista (67), Zemo – Azara (77). Unpublished records: Georgia: Adjaria (6), 2 ♂♂, 30.vi.2013, Chvojka leg., SW, INS 30708 and 30794. Abkhazia: Azgara – Narzan (10), 2 ♂♂, 1.viii.1985, INS 30601 and 30602. Clou (23), 3 ♂♂, 8.viii.1988, INS 2584, 30112 and 30308. Dou near Bzyb (27), 1 ♂, 22.vii.1988, INS 30113. Dvurecje near Dou (28), 5 ♂♂, 20. and 21.vii.1988, INS 30109, 30110, 30111 30307 and 30310. Kelasuri (40), 1 ♂, 25.viii.1985, INS 30408. Niznaja Zemo – Azara (53), 1 ♂, 15.vii.1983, INS 30309. Pskhu (58), 2 ♂♂, 26.vii.1988, INS 2625 and 2626. Resava (61), 1 ♂, 22.vii.1988, INS 30201. Distribution: Transcaucasian species known for tree decades only from Abkhazia (Ježek, 1990c), newly from Georgia, another country than Abkhazia (Oboňa et al., 2019; Ježek et al., 2021a).

Kvazbamormia pskhuensis Ježek, 1995 – Published record: Ježek (1995a): Pskhu (58). Distribution: This species and genus are known so far only from the original description (Ježek, 1995a) from Abkhazia (single locality). See also Oboňa et al. (2019).

Lepimormia georgica (Wagner, 1981) – Published record: Ježek (2004b): Pskhu (58). Unpublished records: Abkhazia: Mercheuli (51), 1 ♂, 5.vii.1983, INS 30524. Pskhu (58), 4 ♂♂, 27. – 29.vii.1988, INS 30031, 30032, 30322 and 30323. Distribution: Transcaucasian species, known from the original description from Georgia (Wagner, 1981) and Abkhazia (Ježek, 2004b).

Mormia ckvitariorum Ježek, 1987 – Published records: Ježek (1987): Achalseni (2), Kaman (39), Kelasuri (40) and Novyj Afon near Anuchva (54). Unpublished records: Abkhazia: Clou (23), 1 ♂, 8.viii.1988, INS 2587. GES – Sukhumi (33), 1 ♂, 3.viii.1988, INS 30116. Macara (49), 2 ♂♂, 5.vii.1983, INS 30513 and 30515. Mercheuli (51), 1 ♂, 5.vii.1983, INS 30514. Otap (57), 1 ♂, 10.viii.1988, INS 30117. Tkvarceli (72), 1 ♂, 11.viii.1988, INS 30204. Distribution: Species of Greater Caucasus: Abkhazia and Azerbaijan (Ježek, 1987; Ježek et al., 2021a).

Promormia silesiensis Ježek, 1983 – Unpublished record: Georgia: Adjaria (6), 1 ♂, 30.vi.2013, Chvojka leg., SW, INS 30832. Distribution: European species, known from Czech Republic, Germany, Greece, Poland, Slovakia, Slovenia (Kročá & Ježek, 2015) and penetrates into Transcaucasia – Azerbaijan (Ježek et al., 2021a). New for Georgia.

Psychomormia vaillanti (Wagner, 1977) – Unpublished record: Abkhazia: Azgara (9), 1 ♂, 21.vii.1983, INS 30564. Distribution: A very rare European species thus far known only from Germany and the Czech Republic so far (Ježek et al., 2019). New for Abkhazia and Transcaucasia.

Yomormia achalshenica Ježek, 1987 – Published records: Ježek (1987): Achalseni (2) and Novyj Afon near Anuchva (54). Unpublished records: Abkhazia: Macara (49), 1 ♂, 4.vii.1983, INS 30482. Mercheuli (51), 1 ♂, 5.vii.1983, INS 30483. Zemo – Azara (77), 1 ♂, 14.vii.1983, INS 30569. Armenia: Shvanidzor (68), 1 ♂, 26.ix.2018, Šumpich leg., SW, INS 30673. Vedi (75), 1 ♂, 30.ix.2018, Šumpich leg., SW, INS 30674. Distribution: This species was thus far known only by its original description (Ježek, 1987) from Abkhazia. New for Armenia.

Yomormia afonensis Ježek, 1987 – Published records: Ježek (1987): Novyj Afon near Anuchva (54). Unpublished records: Abkhazia: Kaldachvara (37), 1 ♂, 1.viii.1988, INS 30083. Macara (49), 1 ♂, 4.vii.1983, INS 30484. Otap (57), 1 ♂, 10.viii.1988, INS 30082. Pskhu (58), 2 ♂♂, 28.vii.1988, INS 30279 and 30280. Distribution: This species was thus far

known only by its original description (Ježek, 1987) from Abkhazia.

Yomormia furva (Tonnoir, 1940) – Published records: Ježek (1987): Novyj Afon near Anuchva (54) and Zemo – Azara (77). Unpublished records: Georgia: Adjaria (6), 1 ♂, 1.vii.2013, Chvojka leg., SW, INS 30796. Abkhazia: Azgara (9), 1 ♂, 21.vii.1983, INS 30518. Azgara – Narzan (10), 1 ♂, 1.viii.1985, INS 30605. Baskacara (11), 2 ♂♂, 18.vii.1983, INS 30209 and 30520. Dvurecje near Dou (28), 1 ♂, 20.vii.1988, INS 30121. Gencvici (32), 2 ♂♂, 7.vii.1983, INS 30212 and 30712. Levj Ptys (48), 1 ♂, 22.vii.1983, INS 30019. Pskhu (58), 1 ♂, 25.vii.1988, INS 30319. Saken (64), 1 ♂, 8.vii.1983, INS 30711. Saken – Narzan (65), 5 ♂♂, 9. and 12.vii.1983, INS 30021, 30022, 30210, 30211 and 30713. Saken near Juznyj Prijut Pass (66), 2 ♂♂, 8.vii.1983, INS 30521 and 30715. Zemo – Azara (77), 3 ♂♂, 10. and 14.vii.1983, INS 30320, 30519 and 30714. Distribution: Western European species (Wagner, 1990, 2019), penetrates into Abkhazia (Ježek, 1987). New for Georgia.

Parajungiella abchazica Ježek, 1985 – Published record: Ježek (1985): Saken – Narzan (65). Unpublished records: Abkhazia: Achalsopeli (1), 1 ♂, 1.viii.1988, INS 30066. Achalseni near Sroma (3), 1 ♂, 15.viii.1985, INS 30468. Acigvara (4), 1 ♂, 6.viii.1988, INS 2599. Anaria (7), 1 ♂, 7.viii.1988, INS 30068. Azgara (9), 2 ♂♂, 21.vii.1983, INS 30480 and 30565. Below Maruch Pass (14), 1 ♂, 16.vii.1983, INS 30474. Beslachuba (16), 2 ♂♂, 11.viii.1988, INS 29070 and 30171. Cebelda (18), 2 ♂♂, 4.viii.1988, INS 2609 and 30072. Cimuri (20), 4 ♂♂, 13.viii.1985, INS 1375, 1381, 30368 and 30371. Cchalta (22), 3 ♂♂, 15. and 22.vii.1983, INS 30477, 30478 and 30765. Clou (23), 3 ♂♂, 8.viii.1988, INS 2585, 30069 and 30270. Dvurecje near Dou (28), 2 ♂♂, 20.vii.1988, INS 30074 and 30075. Dzgerda (29), 2 ♂♂, 2.viii.1988, INS 30067 and 30166. Gencvici (32), 2 ♂♂, 7.vii.1983, INS 30170 and 30670. Ilori (34), 1 ♂, 7.viii.1988, INS 29072. Kaldachvara (37), 1 ♂, 1.viii.1988, INS 30077. Kaldachvara near Mjusoera (38), 1 ♂, 1.viii.1988, INS 2603. Kelasuri (40), 2 ♂♂, 25.viii.1985, INS 30370 and 30467. Kingdi (41), 3 ♂♂, 24.viii.1985, INS 30366, 30567 and 30665. Kochora (42), 1 ♂, 6.viii.1988, INS 30073. Kutol (46), 1 ♂, 2.viii.1988, INS 30273. Levj Ptys (48), 3 ♂♂, 21. – 22.vii.1983, INS 29071, 29074 and 30465. Macara (49), 4 ♂♂, 4.vii.1983 and 18.viii.1985, INS 30367, 39470, 30476 and 30669. Mercheuli (51), 2

♂♂, 5.vii.1983, INS 30277 and 30768. Niznaja Zemo – Azara (53), 1 ♂, 15.vii.1983, INS 30274. Novyj Afon near Anuchva (54), 1 ♂, 19.viii.1985, INS 29076. Okumi (56), 2 ♂♂, 9.viii.1988, INS 30071 and 30079. Otap (57), 5 ♂♂, 10.viii.1988, INS 2605, 30070, 30076, 30080 and 30172. Pskhu (58), 22 ♂♂, 25. – 29.vii.1988, INS 2571, 2614, 2621, 29065, 29066, 29067, 29068, 29069, 29073, 29079, 30065, 30081, 30265, 30266, 30268, 30269, 30275, 30276, 30667, 30766 and 30767. Pskhu near Dou (59), 2 ♂♂, 25.vii.1988, INS 29077 and 29078. Reka near Gali (60), 1 ♂, 7.viii.1988, INS 2606. Sagra near Tamys (63), 1 ♂, 21.viii.1985, INS 30479. Saken (64), 4 ♂♂, 8.vii.1983, INS 30165, 30234, 30668 and 30672. Saken – Narzan (65), 10 ♂♂, 9. and 12.vii.1983, INS 29075, 30167, 30168, 30271, 30272, 30473, 30566, 30666, 30671 and 30769. Saken near Juznyj Prijut Pass (66), 1 ♂, 8.vii.1983, INS 30471. Serbista (67), 1 ♂, 2.viii.1985, INS 30369. Sroma (70), 1 ♂, 15.viii.1985, INS 30472. Tamys (71), 1 ♂, 21.viii.1985, INS 30365. Tkvarceli (72), 1 ♂, 11.viii.1988, INS 30169. Ubus (73), 1 ♂, 7.viii.1985, INS 30568. Zemo – Azara (77), 6 ♂♂, 10. and 15.vii.1983, INS 30267, 30469, 30475, 30481, 30770 and 30771. Distribution: This species was thus far known only by its original description (Ježek, 1985) from Abkhazia and additionally from Armenia (Ježek et al., 2018).

Paramormia (Paramormia) polyascoidea (Krek, 1971) – Published record: Ježek (1990b): Saken – Narzan (65). Unpublished records: Abkhazia: Azgara – Narzan (10), 1 ♂, 1.viii.1985, INS 30648. Cchalta (22), 1 ♂, 15.vii.1983, INS 30824. Gali (31), 1 ♂, 6.viii.1988, INS 30154. Gencvici (32), 2 ♂♂, 7.vii.1983, INS 30246 and 30748. Kutol (46), 1 ♂, 2.viii.1988, INS 30354. Levjy Ptys (48), 1 ♂, 21.vii.1983, INS 30547. Niznaja Zemo – Azara (53), 1 ♂, 15.vii.1983, INS 30356. Novyj Afon near Anuchva (54), 2 ♂♂, 19.viii.1985, INS 30060 and 30646. Pskhu (58), 5 ♂♂, 28. and 29.vii.1988, INS 30062, 30064, 30153, 30353 and 30357. Pskhu near Dou (59), 2 ♂♂, 25.vii.1988, INS 30061 and 30063. Saken (64), 2 ♂♂, 8.vii.1983, INS 30247 and 30750. Saken – Narzan (65), 5 ♂♂, 9. and 12.vii.1983, INS 30059, 30245, 30355, 30747 and 30749. Saken near Juznyj Prijut Pass (66), 1 ♂, 8.vii.1983, INS 30546. Sroma (70), 1 ♂, 15.viii.1985, INS 30549. Zemo – Azara (77), 2 ♂♂, 14. and 15.vii.1983, INS 30548 and 30647. Distribution: European and west Siberian species, known also from Abkhazia and Armenia (Ježek et al., 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021b).

Paramormia (Duckhousiella) ustulata (Walker, 1856) – Unpublished records: Abkhazia: Ocamcira (55), 1 ♂, 21.viii.1985, INS 30463. Armenia: Areni (8), F, 29.ix.2018, Šumpich leg., SW, INS 30833. Lehvaz (47), F, 24.ix.2018, Šumpich leg., SW, INS 30764. Shvanidzor (68), F, 26.ix.2018, Šumpich leg., SW, INS 30763. Yerevan (76), 1 ♂, 1.x.2018, Šumpich leg., SW, INS 30834. Distribution: Holarctic species, newly known also Transcaucasia (Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia) – Ježek et al. (2018, 2021a), Oboňa et al. (2019). New for Abkhazia.

Peripsychoda auriculata (Haliday in Curtis, 1839) – Published records: Ježek (2004b): Kaldakhvara near Mjusoera (38) and Otshamtshira (55). Unpublished records: Abkhazia: Achalsopeli (1), 1 ♂, 1.viii.1988, INS 30094. Cchalta (22), 1 ♂, 5.vii.1983, INS 30781. Kingdi (41), 3 ♂♂, 24.viii.1985, INS 30394, 30582 and 30690. Kutol (46), 1 ♂, 2.viii.1988, INS 30290. Okumi (56), 1 ♂, 9.viii.1988, INS 30095. Otap (57), 1 ♂, 10.viii.1988, INS 30185. Distribution: European species, penetrates into Transcaucasia – Abkhazia, Armenia, Georgia (Wagner, 1981; Ježek, 2004b; Ježek et al., 2018, 2021b).

Seoda ambigua (Eaton, 1893) – Unpublished records: Georgia: Adjaria (6), 2 ♂♂, 30.vi. and 1.vii. 2013, Chvojka leg., SW, INS 30775 and 30776. Distribution: Western Europe (Wagner, 1990, 2019), new for Georgia and Transcaucasia.

Seoda carthusiana (Vaillant, 1972) – Unpublished record: Abkhazia: Saken – Narzan (65), 1 ♂, 9.vii.1983, INS 30795. Distribution: Rather rare species in Europe, locally abundant (Ježek et al., 2019). New for Abkhazia and Transcaucasia.

Seoda svanetica (Ježek, 1989) – Published record: Ježek (1989): Juznyj Prijut Pass (36). Unpublished records: Abkhazia: Baskacara (11), 2 ♂♂, 18.vii.1983, INS 30261 and 30559. Below Maruch Pass (14), 1 ♂, 17.vii.1983, INS 30560. Saken – Narzan (65), 3 ♂♂, 12. and 13.vii.1983, INS 29053, 30362 and 30561. Distribution: A species known only from Transcaucasia: Abkhazia and Georgia (Ježek, 1989; Ježek et al., 2021a).

Philosepedon (Trichosepedon) clouense Ježek, 1994 – Published record: Ježek (1994): Clou (23). Unpublished records: Abkhazia: Baskacara (11), 3 ♂♂, 18.vii.1983, INS 30205, 30206 and 30516. Clou (23), 1 ♂, 8.viii.1988, INS 30312. Kelasuri (40), 1 ♂, 25.viii.1985, INS 30409. Distribution: Greater Caucasus – Abkhazia (Ježek, 1994) and Georgia (Oboňa et al., 2019).

Philosepedon (Trichosepedon) balkanicum Krek, 1971 – Published record: Ježek (2004b): Rica (62). Unpublished records: Georgia: Adjaria (6), 1 ♂, 30.vi.2013, Chvojka leg., light, INS 30591, 1 ♂, 12.vii.1983, INS 30004. Distribution: Known from Western and Central Europe, as well from Abkhazia (Ježek, 2004b). New for Georgia.

Threticus balkaneopalpinus Krek, 1972 – Published records: Ježek (1995c, 2004b): Bzyb (17), Cimuri (20), Pskhu (58), Rica (62) and Zemo – Azara (77). Unpublished records: Georgia: Adjaria (6), 4 ♂♂, 30.vi. and 1.vii.2013, Chvojka leg., SW, INS 30694, 30782, 30785 and 30786. Abkhazia: Azgara (9), 5 ♂♂, 16. and 21.vii.1983, INS 29095, 29096, 30496, 30497 and 30499. Azgara – Narzan (10), 4 ♂♂, 1.viii.1985, INS 30585, 30586, 30587 and 30702. Baskacara (11), 6 ♂♂, 18.vii.1983, INS 30001, 30002, 30192, 30194, 30195 and 30502. Below Adanga Pass (12), 4 ♂♂, 3. and 4.viii.1985, INS 30395, 30399, 30501 and 30691. Below Maruch Pass (14), 6 ♂♂, 17.vii.1983, and 3.viii.1985, INS 29091, 30000, 30297, 30504, 30505 and 30589. Bzyb (17), 2 ♂♂, 5.viii.1985, INS 30397 and 30506. Clou (23), 2 ♂♂, 8.viii.1988, INS 30098 and 30301. Cerna Voda (24), 4 ♂♂, 5.viii.1985, INS 30379, 30390, 30400 and 30698. Dvurecje near Dou (28), 2 ♂♂, 20.vii.1988, INS 30096 and 30099. Kot – Kot near Cimuri (44), 4 ♂♂, 11. and 12.viii.1985, INS 30401, 30583, 30590 and 30695. Levyj Ptys (48), 3 ♂♂, 21. and 22.vii.1983, INS 29090, 29098 and 30495. Maruch near Adanga (50), 1 ♂, 3.viii.1985, INS 30584. Otap (57), 2 ♂♂, 10.viii.1988, INS 30100 and 30189. Pskhu (58), 11 ♂♂, 25. – 29.vii.1988, INS 29093, 30097, 30102, 30190, 30291, 30292, 30293, 30294, 30296, 30693 and 30784. Pskhu near Dou (59), 3 ♂♂, 25.vii.1988, INS 29094, 29097 and 30302. Resava (61), 1 ♂, 22.vii.1988, INS 30188. Rica (62), M, 5.viii.1988, INS 30101. Saken (64), 2 ♂♂, 8.vii.1983, INS 30187 and 30699. Saken – Narzan (65), 14 ♂♂, 9. – 13.vii.1983, INS 29092, 29099, 30003, 30191, 30193, 30295, 30299, 30300, 30500, 30503, 30696, 30700, 30701 and 30783. Serbista (67), 2 ♂♂, 2.viii.1985, INS 30398 and 30692. Tkvarceli (72), 1 ♂, 11.viii.1988, INS 30186. Ubus (73), 3 ♂♂, 7.viii.1985, INS 30396, 30588 and 30697. Zemo – Azara (77), 2 ♂♂, 10. and 15.vii.1983, INS 30298 and 30498. Distribution: Known from Western and Central Europe, as well from Abkhazia (Ježek 1995c, 2004b), from Georgia s. str. (Ježek et al., 2021a).

Threticus negrobovi Vaillant, 1972 – Published records: Ježek (2004b): Pskhu (58), Rica (62).

Unpublished records: Abkhazia: Mercheuli (51), 1 ♂, 5.vii.1983, INS 30810. Pskhu (58), 1 ♂, 25.vii.1988, INS 30047. Distribution: Abkhazia, Czech Republic, Russia, Slovakia, Slovenia (Wagner, 1990; Ježek, 2004b; Ježek et al., 2021b, appendix).

Threticus petrosus Ježek, 1997 – Published record: Ježek (1997): Kot – Kot (43). Unpublished records: Abkhazia: Baskacara (11), 3 ♂♂, 18.vii.1983, INS 30056, 30237 and 30542. Below Adanga Pass (12), 1 ♂, 3.viii.1985, INS 30444. Kot – Kot near Cimuri (44), 4 ♂♂, 10. and 11.viii.1985, INS 30445, 30541, 30543 and 30643. Kot – Kot near Ulm Pass (45), 1 ♂, 10.viii.1985, INS 30540. Serbista (67), 1 ♂, 2.viii.1985, INS 30744. Ubus (73), 1 ♂, 7.viii.1985, INS 30743. Distribution: This species was known so far only by its original description (Ježek, 1997) from Abkhazia (single locality).

Trichopsychoda hirtella (Tonnoir, 1919) – Unpublished record: Abkhazia: Kaman (39), 1 ♂, 15.viii.1985, INS 30530. Distribution: European species, more details see Ježek et al. (2020). New for Abkhazia and Transcaucasia.

Chodopsycha buxtoni (Withers, 1988) – Unpublished records: Abkhazia: Azgara – Narzan (10), 1 ♂, 1.viii.1985, INS 30597. Cimuri (20), 1 ♂, 13.viii.1985, INS 30407. Dzgerda (29), 1 ♀, 2.viii.1988, INS 30108. Levyj Ptys (48), 1 ♀, 21.vii.1983, INS 30200. Pskhu (58), 2 ♀♀, 25. and 27.vii.1988, INS 30008 and 30107. Saken – Narzan (65), 2 ♂♂, 13.vii.1983, INS 29080 and 30106. Distribution: European rare species (Great Britain, Czech Republic, and Slovakia only – Ježek et al., 2021b). New for Abkhazia and Transcaucasia.

Chodopsycha lobata (Tonnoir, 1940) – Published record: Ježek (2004b): Rica (62). Unpublished records: Abkhazia: Azgara (9), 1 ♀, 21.vii.1983, INS 30229. Azgara – Narzan (10), 1 ♂, 3 ♀♀, 1.viii.1985, INS 30626, 30627, 30629 and 30730. Baskacara (11), 3 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, 18.vii.1983, INS 30041, 30227, 30228, 30232 and 30233. Below Maruch Pass (14), 1 ♀, 3.vii.1985, INS 30628. Bzyb (17), 1 ♀, 5.viii.1985, INS 30533. Dvurecje near Dou (28), 1 ♀, 21.vii.1988, INS 30044. Kelasuri (40), 1 ♀, 25.viii.1985, INS 30433. Kot – Kot (43), 1 ♀, 11.viii.1985, INS 30431. Kot – Kot near Cimuri (44), 2 ♀♀, 12.viii.1985, INS 30625 and 30729. Kot – Kot near Ulm Pass (45), 1 ♂, 11.viii.1985, INS 30432. Saken – Narzan (65), 3 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, 9., 12. and 13.vii.1983, INS 30042, 30043, 30136, 30230 and 30231. Serbista (67), 1 ♀, 2.viii.1985, INS 30430. Ubus (73), 2 ♂♂, 7.viii.1985,

INS 30411 and 30731. Distribution: Common European species, Transcaucasian sites represent Abkhazia and Georgia s. str. More information in detail see Ježek et al. (2021a, b).

Copropsychoa brevicornis (Tonnoir, 1940) – Unpublished records: Abkhazia: Sagra near Tamys (63), 1 ♂, 21.viii.1985, INS 30511. Saken – Narzan (65), 1 ♂, 9.vii.1983, INS 30199. Tamys (71), 1 ♀, 21.viii.1985, INS 30406. Distribution: Palaearctic species (Wagner, 1990, 2019; Ježek et al., 2020), known from Georgia (Ježek et al., 2021a). New for Abkhazia.

Logima albipennis (Zetterstedt, 1850) – Unpublished records: Armenia: Areni ARM (8), 1 ♀, 21.ix.2018, Šumpich leg., SW, INS 30571. Yerevan (76), 1 ♀, 1.x.2018, Šumpich leg., SW, INS 30772. Abkhazia: Baskacara (11), M, 4 ♀♀, 18.vii.1983, INS 29081, 29082, 30173, 30181 and 30486. Below Adanga Pass (12), 1 ♀, 4.viii.1985, INS 30485. Below Maruch Pass (14), 2 ♀♀, 2 ♂♂, 17.vii.1983 and 3.viii.1985, INS 30175, 30179, 30180 and 30572. Cimuri (20), 1 ♀, 10.viii.1985, INS 30487. Dou Pass (26), 1 ♂, 21.vii.1988, INS 29083. Rica (62), 1 ♀, 5.viii.1988, INS 2591. Saken – Narzan (65), 5 ♀♀, 1 ♂, 9., 12. and 13.vii.1983, INS 29080, 30084, 30174, 30176, 30177 and 30178. Ubus (73), F, 7.viii.1985, INS 30675. Distribution: A cosmopolitan species, data in details with a new report for Georgia see Ježek et al. (2021a). Known from Armenia and Azerbaijan (Ježek et al., 2018). New for Abkhazia.

Logima erminea (Eaton, 1893) – Published records: Ježek (2004b): Tshlou (23), Pskhu (58). Unpublished records: Abkhazia: Beslachuba (16), 1 ♀, 11.viii.1988, INS 30208. Clou (23), 1 ♀, 8.viii.1988, INS 30314. Kelasuri (40), 1 ♀, 25.viii.1985, INS 30413. Mercheuli (51), 1 ♂, 5.vii.1983, INS 30017. Novyj Afon near Anuchva (54), 1 ♀, 19.viii.1985, INS 30015. Pskhu (58), 2 ♂♂, 1 ♀, 25. and 28.vii.1988, INS 30016, 30316 and 30317. Pskhu near Dou (59), 1 ♂, 1 ♀, 25.vii.1988, INS 30018 and 30315. Zemo – Azara (77), 1 ♂, 15.vii.1983, INS 30207. Distribution: Palaearctic species, known from Western, Northern and Central Europe, North Africa, Taiwan, Japan, penetrates into Abkhazia in Transcaucasia (Ježek, 2004b; Ježek et al., 2021b).

Logima satchelli (Quate, 1955) – Unpublished records: Armenia: Areni (8), 1 ♀, 29.ix.2018, Šumpich leg., SW, INS 30828. Georgia: Adjaria (6), 2 ♂♂, 30.vi. and 1.vii.2013, Chvojka leg., SW, INS 30829 and 30830. Abkhazia: Azgara – Narzan (10), 1 ♂,

1.viii.1985, INS 30659. Below Adanga Pass (12), 1 ♀, 4.viii.1985, INS 30553. Below Maruch Pass (14), 1 ♂, 3.viii.1985, INS 30658. Dvurecje near Dou (28), 1 ♀, 20.vii.1988, INS 30155. Saken – Narzan (65), 2 ♂♂, 13.vii.1983, INS 29051 and 30156. Serbista (67), 1 ♂, 2.viii.1985, INS 30455. Distribution: Holarctic species, known also from Azerbaijan (Ježek et al., 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021a, b), new for Abkhazia, Armenia, and Georgia.

Logima zetterstedti Ježek, 1983 – Unpublished records: Abkhazia: Below Maruch Pass (14), 1 ♂, 17.vii.1983, INS 30260. Serbista, ABK (67), 1 ♂, 2.viii.1985, INS 30464. Distribution: In the first place European and west Siberian species; however, in the case of a verification probably cosmopolitan species (Ježek et al., 2019, 2021b). New for Abkhazia and Transcaucasia.

Psycha grisescens (Tonnoir, 1922) – Unpublished records: Abkhazia: Below Adanga Pass (12), 1 ♂, 3.viii.1985, INS 30420. Kaman (39), F, 15.viii.1985, INS 30526. Kelasuri (40), 1 ♀, 25.viii.1985, INS 30419. Kot – Kot near Cimuri (44), 1 ♂, 12.viii.1985, INS 30609. Saken – Narzan (65), 4 ♂♂, 13.vii.1983, INS 30036, 30127, 30128 and 30225. Ubus (73), 1 ♂, 7.viii.1985, INS 30718. Distribution: European species, registered in Central Anatolia and North Africa, penetrates into Transcaucasia (Azerbaijan) (Oboňa et al., 2019; Ježek et al., 2021a). New for Abkhazia.

Psychoda alticola Vaillant, 1973 – Unpublished records: Abkhazia: Baskacara (11), 1 ♂, 18.vii.1983, INS 30489. Below Adanga Pass (12), 1 ♂, 3.viii.1985, INS 30375. Levyj Ptys (48), 1 ♂, 22.vii.1983, INS 30183. Serbista (67), 1 ♂, 2.viii.1985, INS 30376. Ubus (73), 1 ♂, 7.viii.1985, INS 30679. Distribution: West and Central European species (Wagner, 1990, 2019; Ježek et al., 2021b, appendix). New for Abkhazia and Transcaucasia.

Psychoda crassipennis Tonnoir, 1940 – Unpublished records: Abkhazia: Saken – Narzan (65), 1 ♂, 13.vii.1983, INS 30119. Serbista (67), M, 2.viii.1985, INS 30710. Distribution: Western, Northern and Central Europe (Ježek, 2009; Ježek et al., 2019). New for Abkhazia and Transcaucasia.

Psychoda phalaenoides (Linnaeus, 1758) – Unpublished records: Abkhazia: Adanga Pass (5), 1 ♂, 4.viii.1985, INS 30745. Baskacara (11), 1 ♀, 18.vii.1983, INS 30239. Below Adanga Pass (12), 1 ♂, 4.viii.1985, INS 30544. Below Maruch Pass (14), 2 ♂♂, F, 17.vii.1983 and 3.viii.1985, INS 30242, 30244

and 30644. Bzyb (17), 1 ♀, 5.viii.1985, INS 30446. Clou (23), F, 8.viii.1988, INS 30351. Dou Pass (26), 1 ♀, 22.vii.1988, INS 30151. Kaman (39), 1 ♂, 15.viii.1985, INS 30545. Kelasuri (40), 1 ♂, 25.viii.1985, INS 30447. Mercheuli (51), 1 ♀, 5.vii.1983, INS 30057. Mramba (52), 1 ♀, 4.viii.1988, INS 30152. Saken – Narzan (65), 4 ♂♂, 1 ♀, 12. and 13.vii.1983, INS 30058, 30149, 30150, 30241 and 30243. Serbista (67), 1 ♂, 1 ♀, 2.viii.1985, INS 30448 and 30746. Ubus (73), 1 ♂, 7.viii.1985, INS 30449. Zemo – Azara (77), 1 ♀, 10.vii.1983, INS 30238. Georgia: Svanetia (69), 1 ♀, 5.vii.2013, Chvojka leg., at light, INS 30822. Distribution: Holarctic species, known from Azerbaijan and Georgia, as well; for details see Oboňa et al. (2019) and Ježek et al. (2020, 2021a, b). New for Abkhazia.

Psychoda uniformata Haseman, 1907 – Unpublished records: Abkhazia: Ocamcira (55), 1 ♀, 21.viii.1985, INS 30461. Pskhu near Dou (59), 1 ♂, 25.vii.1988, INS 29064. Tamys (71), 1 ♀, 21.viii.1985, INS 30462. Distribution: Holarctic species, also newly known from Transcaucasia (Armenia, Azerbaijan) (Ježek et al., 2018, 2021b; Oboňa et al., 2019). New for Abkhazia.

Psychodocha cinerea (Banks, 1894) – Published record: Ježek (1990a): Cimuri (20). Unpublished records: Russia: Dagomys (25), 1 ♀, 1. – 5.ix.1982, Dlabola leg., SW, INS 30009. Abkhazia: GES – Suchumi (33), 1 ♀, 3.viii.1988, INS 30202. Kaldachvara (37), 1 ♀, 1.vii.1988, INS 30114. Kaman (39), 1 ♀, 15.viii.1985, INS 30512. Mramba (52), 1 ♂, 4.viii.1988, INS 30115. Novyj Afon near Anuchva (54), 1 ♀, 19.viii.1985, INS 30603. Pskhu (58), 1 ♀, 29.vii.1988, INS 30010. Saken – Narzan (65), 1 ♀, 12.vii.1983, INS 30203. Distribution: Cosmopolitan species, published as well from Russia (Siberia – Ježek, 1992b), detailed information incl. Abkhazia (Ježek, 1990a), Georgia and Armenia (Ježek et al., 2021a).

Psychodocha gemina (Eaton, 1904) – Published records: Ježek (1990a): Cimuri (20) and Juznyj Prijut Pass (36). Unpublished records: Abkhazia: Achalseni (2), 1 ♀, 14.viii.1985, INS 30522. Baskacara (11), 1 ♂, 6 F, 17. and 18.vii.1983, INS 30023, 30024, 30027, 30214, 30218, 30219 and 30224. Below Maruch Pass (14), 2 ♀♀, 17.vii.1983 and 3.viii.1985, INS 30215 and 30606. Cebelda (18), 2 F, 4.viii.1988, INS 2612 and 30216. Cchalta (22), 1 ♀, 15.vii.1983, INS 30025. Gencvici (32), 1 ♀, 7.vii.1983, INS 30026. Kaman (39), 1 ♀, 15.viii.1985, INS 30523. Kot – Kot near

Cimuri (44), 1 ♂, 12.viii.1985, INS 30607. Levyj Ptys (48), F, 21.vii.1983, INS 30222. Mramba (52), 1 ♂, 4.viii.1988, INS 30124. Niznaja Zemo – Azara (53), 1 ♂, 15.vii.1983, INS 30029. Pskhu (58), 1 ♀, 1 ♂, 26. and 27.vii.1988, INS 2728 and 30123. Rica (62), 1 ♂, 2 ♀♀, 5.vii.1988, INS 2594, 2597 and 30125. Saken (64), 1 ♀, 8.vii.1983, INS 30220. Saken – Narzan (65), 4 ♀♀, 4 ♂♂, 11. – 13.vii.1983, INS 30020, 30028, 30030, 30122, 30213, 30217, 30221 and 30223. Serbista (67), 2 ♀♀, 2.viii.1985, INS 30416 and 30716. Distribution: European species, also penetrates into Transcaucasia (Abkhazia, Azerbaijan, Georgia) – (Wagner, 1990, 2019; Ježek et al., 2021a).

Psychodula minuta (Banks, 1894) – Published record: Ježek (1990a): Cimuri (20). Unpublished records: Georgia: Adjaria (6), 1 ♀, 1.vii.2013, Chvojka leg., SW, INS 30802. Abkhazia: Baskacara (11), 1 ♀, 18.vii.1983, INS 30045. Kot – Kot near Cimuri (44), 1 ♀, 12.viii.1985, INS 30630. Mercheuli (51), 1 ♂, 5.vii.1983, INS 30046. Tamys (71), 1 ♂, 21.viii.1985, INS 30434. Distribution: Holarctic species, from Europe penetrates into Transcaucasia (Abkhazia), more details see Ježek et al. (2020, 2021b). New for Georgia.

Psychomora trinodulosa (Tonnoir, 1922) – Unpublished records: Abkhazia: Achalseni (2), 1 ♀, 14.viii.1985, INS 30562. Acigvara (4), 1 ♀, 6.viii.1988, INS 2600. Azgara – Narzan (10), 1 ♂, 1.viii.1985, INS 30761. Below Maruch Pass (14), 1 ♂, 3.viii.1985, INS 30662. Cebelda (18), 2 ♀♀, 4.viii.1988, INS 30164 and 30258. Clou (23), 2 ♀♀, 8.viii.1988, INS 2588 and 30364. Gali (31), 1 ♂, 6.viii.1988, INS 30162. Gencvici (32), 1 ♀, 7.vii.1983, INS 29061. Kaman (39), 1 ♀, 15.viii.1985, INS 30563. Kelasuri (40), 1 ♂, 25.viii.1985, INS 30460. Mercheuli (51), 1 ♂, 5.vii.1983, INS 29056. Mramba (52), 1 ♀, 4.viii.1988, INS 30163. Niznaja Zemo – Azara (53), 1 ♀, 15.vii.1983, INS 29063. Novyj Afon near Anuchva (54), 1 ♂, 19.viii.1985, INS 29057. Okumi (56), 3 ♂♂, 9.viii.1988, INS 30160, 30161 and 30253. Pskhu (58), 1 ♂, 26.vii.1988, INS 29055. Pskhu near Dou (59), 1 ♀, 1 ♂, 25.vii.1988, INS 29058 and 30363. Reka near Gali (60), 1 ♂, 7.viii.1988, INS 2607. Sagra near Tamys (63), 1 ♀, 21.viii.1985, INS 30459. Saken (64), 1 ♂, 1 ♀♀, 8.vii.1983, INS 29062 and 30251. Saken – Narzan (65), 2 ♂♂, 2 ♀♀, 9., 11. and 12.vii.1983, INS 30159, 30252 30254 and 30256. Serbista (67), 1 ♂, 2.viii.1985, INS 30762. Zemo – Azara (77), 3 ♂♂, 3 ♀♀, 10., 14. and 15.vii.1983, INS 29054, 29059, 29060, 30250, 30255 and 30257. Distribution:

Holarctic species, known from Azerbaijan and Georgia; see some details e. g. in Ježek et al. (2019, 2020, 2021a, b) and Oboňa et al. (2019). New for Abkhazia.

Tinearia alternata (Say, 1824) – Unpublished records: Armenia: Areni (8), 2 ♀♀, 21. and 29.ix.2018, Šumpich leg., SW, INS 30573 and 30773. Shvanidzor (68), 1 ♀, 26.ix.2018, Šumpich leg., SW, INS 30677. Yerevan (76), 1 ♀, 1.x.2018, Šumpich leg., SW, INS 30774. Abkhazia: Azgara – Narzan (10), 1 ♂, 1.viii.1985, INS 30678. Cebelda (18), F, 4.viii.1988, INS 2611. Cimuri (20), 2 ♀♀, 10. and 13.viii.1985, INS 1378 and 30488. Gali (31), 1 ♂, 6.viii.1988, INS 30085. Macara (49), 1 ♂, 5 ♀♀, 5. and 24.vii.1983, 17. and 18.viii.1985, 3. and 10.viii.1988, INS 29084, 29086, 30090, 30182, 30374 and 30676. Mercheuli (51), 1 ♀, 5.vii.1983, INS 29085. Mramba (52), 2 ♀♀, 4.viii.1988, INS 30088 and 30089. Ocamcira (55), 1 ♀, 21.viii.1985, INS 30372. Okumi (56), 1 ♂, 9.viii.1988, INS 30087. Pskhu (58), 2 ♂♂, 26. and 27.vii.1988, INS 2619 and 30281. Reka near Gali (60), 1 ♂, 7.viii.1988, INS 2608. Tamys (71), F, 21.viii.1985, INS 30373. Distribution: A cosmopolitan species, known from Armenia and Azerbaijan (Ježek et al., 2018), data from Georgia see Oboňa et al. (2019) and Ježek et al. (2021a). New for Abkhazia.

Tinearia lativentris (Berdén, 1952) – Unpublished record: Armenia: Areni (8), 1 ♀, 29.9.2018, Šumpich leg., SW, INS 30801. Distribution: Holarctic species, for detailed information see Ježek et al. (2021b). New for Armenia and Transcaucasia.

Ypsydocha setigera (Tonnoir, 1922) – Unpublished record: Abkhazia: Azgara (9), 1 ♂, 21.vii.1983, INS 30262. Baskacara (11), 1 ♂, 18.vii.1983, INS 29052. Kot – Kot near Ulm Pass (45), 1 ♂, 11.viii.1985, INS 30456. Saken – Narzan (65), 5 ♀♀, 9. – 13.vii.1983, INS 30157, 30158, 30249, 30263 and 30264. Serbista (67), 1 ♀, 2.viii.1985, INS 30457. Ubus (73), 1 ♀, 7.viii.1985, INS 30458. Distribution: Holarctic species, known from Georgia (Oboňa et al., 2019), some additional information in Ježek et al. (2019, 2021b). New for Abkhazia.

Berdeniella caucasica Wagner, 1981 – Unpublished records: Abkhazia: Gencvici (32), 1 ♂, 7.vii.1983, INS 30707. Saken – Narzan (65), 1 ♂, 13.vii.1983, INS 30598. Ubus (73), 1 ♂, 7.viii.1985, INS 30600. Zemo – Azara (77), 1 ♂, 10.vii.1983, INS 30599. Distribution: Known only from the original description (Wagner, 1981) from the western Caucasus (Russian village Taberda). New for Abkhazia.

Berdeniella manicata (Tonnoir, 1920) – Unpublished record: Abkhazia: Pskhu (58), 1 ♂, 27.vii.1988, INS 30332. Distribution: European species, penetrates into Transcaucasia (Georgia) – see Oboňa et al. (2019) and Ježek et al. (2020, 2021b). New for Abkhazia.

Berdeniella schumpkanica Vaillant & Joost, 1983 – Unpublished records: Abkhazia: Adanga Pass (5), 1 ♂, 4.viii.1985, INS 30556. Baskacara (11), 2 ♂♂, 18.vii.1983, INS 30361 and 30759. Below Chimsa Pass (13), 1 ♂, 8.viii.1985, INS 30555. Below Ulm Pass (15), 1 ♂, 9.viii.1985, INS 30661. Chimsa near Ulm (19), 1 ♂, 11.viii.1985, INS 30664. Juznyj Prijut Pass (36), 1 ♂, 7.vii.1983, INS 30557. Saken – Narzan (65), 1 ♂, 12.vii.1983, INS 30558. Ubus (73), 2 ♂♂, 7.viii.1985, INS 30663 and 30760. Ubus near Bzyb (74), 1 ♂, 7.viii.1985, INS 30554. Zemo – Azara (77), 2 ♂♂, 10.vii.1983, INS 30660 and 30758. Georgia: Svanetia (69), 1 ♂, 5.vii.2013, Chvojka leg., SW, INS 30831. Distribution: A species described from northern adjacent Caucasian slope in Russia (Vaillant & Joost, 1983 – Terskol + stream Schumka). New for Abkhazia and Georgia.

Clytocerus (Boreoclytocerus) grusanicus Wagner, 1981 – Unpublished records: Georgia: Adjaria (6), 2 ♂♂, 30.vi. and 1.vii.2013, Chvojka leg., SW, INS 30721 and 30800. Svanetia (69), 1 ♂, 4.vii.2013, Chvojka leg., SW, INS 30617. Abkhazia: Azgara (9), 1 ♂, 21.vii.1983, INS 30612. Azgara – Narzan (10), 4 ♂♂, 1.viii.1985, INS 30611, 30615, 30619 and 30723. Baskacara (11), 1 ♂, 18.vii.1983, INS 30725. Cchalta (22), 2 ♂♂, 15. and 22.vii.1983, INS 30326 and 30719. Clou (23), 2 ♂♂, 8.viii.1988, INS 30134 and 30330. Dvurecje near Dou (28), 2 ♂♂, 20.vii.1988, INS 30132 and 30133. Gagra (30), 1 ♂, 23.viii.1985, INS 30614. Gencvici (32), 1 ♂, 7.vii.1983, INS 30724. Kelasuri (40), 1 ♂, 25.viii.1985, INS 30422. Levyj Ptys (48), 4 ♂♂, 21. and 22.vii.1983, INS 30421, 30423, 30427 and 30528. Macara (49), 1 ♂, 18.viii.1985, INS 30426. Mercheuli (51), 1 ♂, 5.vii.1983, INS 30613. Niznaja Zemo – Azara (53), 1 ♂, 15.vii.1983, INS 30610. Otap (57), 2 ♂♂, 10.viii.1988, INS 30130 and 30226. Pskhu (58), 5 ♂♂, 27. – 29.vii.1988, INS 30038, 30129, 30131, 30327 and 30722. Pskhu near Dou (59), 2 ♂♂, 25.vii.1988, INS 30037 and 30039. Saken (64), 3 ♂♂, 8.vii.1983, INS 30424, 30527 and 30618. Zemo – Azara (77), 6 ♂♂, 10., 14. and 15.vii.1983, INS 30328, 30425, 30616, 30720, 30726 and 30799. Distribution: Transcaucasian species known from

Georgia (the original description of Wagner, 1981; for the second record, see Oboňa et al., 2019). New for Abkhazia.

Pericoma (Pericoma) bunae Krek, 1979 – Unpublished records: Armenia: Areni (8), 3 ♂♂, 21. and 29.ix.2018, Šumpich leg., SW, INS 30596, 30792 and 30793. Lehvaz (47), 1 ♂, 24.ix.2018, Šumpich leg., SW, INS 30706. Distribution: Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro (Krek, 1999), Azerbaijan (Ježek et al., 2018). New for Armenia.

Pericoma (Pericoma) exquisita Eaton, 1893 – Unpublished records: Abkhazia: Kaman (39), 1 ♂, 15.viii.1985, INS 30517. Kelasuri (40), 1 ♂, 25.viii.1985, INS 30415. Macara (49), 1 ♂, 5.vii.1983, INS 30318. Mercheuli (51), 1 ♂, 5.vii.1983, INS 30604. Okumi (56), 1 ♂, 9.viii.1988, INS 30120. Distribution: Species widespread in Europe, North Africa, and Transcaucasia (Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia) – Ježek et al. (2018, 2021a); Oboňa et al. (2019). New for Abkhazia.

Pericoma (Pericoma) inopinata Ježek, Oboňa & Manko, 2021 – Unpublished records: Abkhazia: Cimuri near Achalseni (21), 1 ♂, 13.viii.1985, INS 30532. Kaman (39), 1 ♂, 15.viii.1985, INS 30531. Mercheuli (51), 2 ♂♂, 5.vii.1983, INS 30623 and 30624. Mramba (52), 1 ♂, 4.viii.1988, INS 30135. Novyj Afon near Anuchva (54), 2 ♂♂, 19.viii.1985, INS 30040 and 30621. Zemo – Azara (77), 1 ♂, 15.vii.1983, INS 30622. Distribution: Transcaucasian species known only from the original description from Azerbaijan and Georgia (Ježek et al., 2021c). New for Abkhazia.

Pericoma (Pericoma) motasi motasi Vaillant, 1978 – Unpublished records: Georgia: Adjara (6), 3 ♂♂, 30.vi.2013, Chvojka leg., SW, INS 30732, 30807 and 30808. Svanetia (69), 1 ♂, 5.vii.2013, Chvojka leg., SW, INS 30809. Abkhazia: Zemo – Azara (77), 1 ♂, 10.vii.1983, INS 30631. Distribution: Species described from the Carpathian Mountains (Romania) by Vaillant (1978), from Bulgaria reported by Wagner & Joost (1988). Known from Georgia now (Oboňa et al., 2019). New for Abkhazia.

Pericoma (Pericoma) pannonica Szabó, 1960 – Unpublished record: Armenia: Areni (8), 1 ♂, 29.ix.2018, Šumpich leg., SW, INS 30821. Distribution: European species (Wagner, 1990, 2019; Ježek et al., 2020, 2021b; appendix). New for Armenia and Transcaucasia.

Pericoma (Pericoma) pseudexquisita Tonnoir, 1940 – Unpublished records: Georgia: Adjara (6), 1 ♂,

30.vi.2013, Chvojka leg., SW, INS 30825. Abkhazia: Baskacara (11), 1 ♂, 17.vii.1983, INS 30826. Cchalta (22), 1 ♂, 22.vii.1983, INS 30358. Levyj Ptys (48), 1 ♂, 22.vii.1983, INS 30550. Zemo – Azara (77), 3 ♂♂, 14. and 15.vii.1983, INS 30450, 30751 and 30827. Distribution: A species registered in Western, Central and Southern Europe, known from Georgia (Ježek et al., 2020, 2021a, b). New for Abkhazia.

Pericoma (Pachypericoma) blandula Eaton, 1893 – Published records: Ježek (2004b): Tshlou (23), Pskhu (58). Unpublished records: Georgia: Adjara (6), 4 ♂♂, 30.vi. and 1.vii.2013, Chvojka leg., SW, INS 30704, 30787, 30789 and 30790. Svanetia (69), 1 ♂, 5.vii.2013, Chvojka leg., SW, INS 30788. Tkvarčeli, ABK (72), 1 ♂, 11.viii.1988, INS 30197. Abkhazia: Achalseni near Sroma (3), 1 ♂, 15.viii.1985, INS 30510. Azgara – Narzan (10), 1 ♂, 1.viii.1985, INS 30592. Cimuri (20), 1 ♂, 13.viii.1985, INS 30509. Clou (23), 2 ♂♂, 8.viii.1988, INS 30104 and 30304. Gencvici (32), 1 ♂, 7.vii.1983, INS 30705. GES – Sukhumi (33), 1 ♂, 3.viii.1988, INS 30196. Kaldachvara (37), 2 ♂♂, 1.viii.1988, INS 30007 and 30103. Kaman (39), 1 ♂, 15.viii.1985, INS 30508. Kelasuri (40), 1 ♂, 25.viii.1985, INS 30403. Levyj Ptys (48), 2 ♂♂, 22.vii.1983, INS 30402 and 30507. Mercheuli (51), 2 ♂♂, 5.vii.1983, INS 30593 and 30595. Novyj Afon near Anuchva (54), 2 ♂♂, 19.viii.1985, INS 30006 and 30594. Otap (57), 1 ♂, 10.viii.1988, INS 30105. Pskhu (58), 4 ♂♂, 25. – 28.vii.1988, INS 30005, 30198, 30303 and 30306. Saken – Narzan (65), 2 ♂♂, 12.vii.1983, INS 30305 and 30703. Zemo – Azara (77), 2 ♂♂, 14. and 15.vii.1983, INS 30405 and 30791. Armenia: Lehvaz (47), 1 ♂, 24.ix.2018, Šumpich leg., SW, INS 30404. Distribution: Known from Western and Central Europe, North Africa, and Transcaucasian Georgia (Wagner, 1990); as well from Abkhazia (Ježek, 2004b), Armenia and Azerbaijan (Ježek et al., 2018).

Pericoma (Pachypericoma) fallax Eaton, 1893 – Published record: Ježek (2004b): Tshlou (23). Distribution: European and West-Siberian species, also known as well from Transcaucasia (Abkhazia, Azerbaijan and Georgia) – Oboňa et al. (2019); Ježek et al. (2021a).

Pneumia compta (Eaton, 1893) – Unpublished record: Abkhazia: Bzyb (17), 1 ♂, 5.viii.1985, INS 30412. Distribution: Western and Central European species (Wagner, 1990, 2019, Ježek et al., 2021b – appendix). New for Abkhazia and Transcaucasia.

Pneumia gracilis gracilis (Eaton, 1893) – Published records: Ježek (2004b): Bzyb (17), Pskhu (58). Unpublished records: Abkhazia: Cimuri (20), 1 ♂, 13.viii.1985, INS 30417. Cimuri near Achalseni (21), 1 ♂, 13.viii.1985, INS 30525. Levyj Ptys (48), 1 ♂, 22.vii.1983, INS 30418. Pskhu (58), 9 ♂♂, 25. – 29.vii.1988, INS 2572, 2617, 30033, 30035, 30126, 30321, 30325, 30717 and 30797. Pskhu near Dou (59), 1 ♂, 25.vii.1988, INS 30034. Zemo – Azara (77), 2 ♂♂, 10. and 15.vii.1983, INS 30608 and 30798. Distribution: European species (Wagner, 1990, 2019), penetrates into Great Caucasus. Detailed information in Ježek et al. (2019).

Pneumia nubila (Meigen, 1818) – Published records: Ježek & Hájek (2007, erratum): Akhalsheni (2), Atshigvara (4), Bzyb (17), Cebelda (18), Cimuri (20), Pskhu (58). Unpublished records: Georgia: Adjara (6), 4 ♂♂, 30.vi. and 1.vii.2013, Chvojka leg., SW, INS 30740, 30811, 30812 and 30813. Imereli (35), 1 ♂, 7.vii.2013, Chvojka leg., SW, INS 30814. Abkhazia: Achalseni (2), 1 ♂, 3.viii.1988, INS 30146. Anaria (7), 1 ♂, 7.viii.1988, INS 30137. Azgara (9), 1 ♂, 21.vii.1983, INS 30818. Azgara – Narzan (10), 2 ♂♂, 1.viii.1985, INS 30641 and 30742. Below Adanga Pass (12), 1 ♂, 3.viii.1985, INS 30435. Beslachuba (16), 1 ♂, 11.viii.1988, INS 30051. Cimuri (20), 1 ♂, 13.viii.1985, INS 30441. Cchalta (22), 1 ♂, 22.vii.1983, INS 30333. Clou (23), 1 ♂, 8.viii.1988, INS 30340. Dvurecje near Dou (28), 2 ♂♂, 20.vii.1988, INS 30138 and 30147. Dzgerda (29), 1 ♂, 2.viii.1988, INS 30235. Gagra (30), 1 ♂, 23.viii.1985, INS 30639. Gencvici (32), 2 ♂♂, 7.vii.1983, INS 30436 and 30735. Kaldachvara (37), 1 ♂, 1.viii.1988, INS 30144. Kaman (39), 1 ♂, 15.viii.1985, INS 30535. Kingdi (41), 3 ♂♂, 24.viii.1985, INS 30440, 30634 and 30734. Kot – Kot near Cimuri (44), 2 ♂♂, 12. and 13.viii.1985, INS 30438 and 30635. Kot – Kot near Ulm Pass (45), 1 ♂, 10.viii.1985, INS 30539. Kutol (46), 1 ♂, 2.viii.1988, INS 30338. Levyj Ptys (48), 2 ♂♂, 21. and 22.vii.1983, INS 30537 and 30538. Macara (49), 5 ♂♂, 4. and 5.vii.1983, 18.viii.1985, INS 30344, 30439, 30442, 30642 and 30737. Mercheuli (51), 3 ♂♂, 5.vii.1983, INS 30633, 30638 and 30736. Mramba (52), 1 ♂, 4.viii.1988, INS 30139. Niznaja Zemo – Azara (53), 1 ♂, 15.vii.1983, INS 30632. Ocancira (55), 1 ♂, 21.viii.1985, INS 30437. Okumi (56), 2 ♂♂, 9.viii.1988, INS 30140 and 30145. Otap (57), 1 ♂, 10.viii.1988, INS 30141. Pskhu (58), 13 ♂♂, 27. – 29.vii.1988, INS 30049, 30050, 30054, 30142, 30143, 30336, 30337, 30341, 30346, 30347,

30739, 30816 and 30819. Pskhu near Dou (59), 4 ♂♂, 25. vii.1988, INS 30048, 30052, 30053 and 30342. Saken (64), 4 ♂♂, 8.vii.1983, INS 30165, 30234, 30668 and 30738. Saken – Narzan (65), 6 ♂♂, 9., 11. and 12.vii.1983, INS 30334, 30335, 30339, 30343, 30443 and 30820. Saken near Juznyj Prijut Pass (66), 1 ♂, 8.vii.1983, INS 30817. Sroma (70), 1 ♂, 15.viii.1985, INS 30536. Tamys (71), 1 ♂, 21.viii.1985, INS 30640. Tkvarceli (72), 1 ♂, 11.viii.1988, INS 30236. Zemo – Azara (77), 6 ♂♂, 10., 14. and 15.vii.1983, INS 30345, 30636, 30637 30733, 30741 and 30815. Distribution: European species, known as well from Transcaucasia (Abkhazia, Armenia, Azerbaijan, and Georgia (details see Ježek et al., 2018, 2020, 2021a).

Pneumia palustris (Meigen, 1804) – Published records: Ježek & Hájek (2007, erratum): Bzyb (17) and Pskhu (58). Unpublished records: Abkhazia: Pskhu (58), 3 ♂♂, 25. and 27.vii.1988, INS 30148, 30348 and 30350. Pskhu near Dou (59), 2 ♂♂, 25.vii.1988, INS 30055 and 30349. Distribution: European species, registered also in Transcaucasia (Abkhazia and Georgia), more information in Ježek et al. (2019, 2020, 2021a) and Oboňa et al. (2019).

Pneumia pilularia (Tonnoir, 1940) – Unpublished records: Armenia: Areni (8), 2 ♂♂, 29.ix.2018, Šumpich leg., SW, INS 30645 and 30823. Abkhazia: Below Maruch Pass (14), 1 ♂, 17.vii.1983, INS 30352. Distribution: A species known almost throughout Europe. It has also been recorded also from Transcaucasia (central Caucasus – Terskol in Russia, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia and Tajikistan) (Ježek et al., 2018, 2021a, b; Oboňa et al., 2019). New for Abkhazia.

Pneumia trivialis (Eaton, 1893) – Unpublished record: Abkhazia: Tkvarceli (72), 1 ♂, 11.viii.1988, INS 30259. Distribution: Ubiquitous European species, known newly as well from Transcaucasia (Azerbaijan and Georgia) (Ježek et al., 2021a, b). New for Abkhazia.

Saraiella resslis Wagner, 1981 – Unpublished records: Abkhazia: Azgara (9), 1 ♂, 21.vii.1983, INS 30649. Azgara – Narzan (10), 3 ♂♂, 1.viii.1985, INS 30651, 30654 and 30752. Baskacara (11), 1 ♂, 18.vii.1983, INS 29050. Below Adanga Pass (12), 1 ♂, 3.viii.1985, INS 30452. Chimsa near Ulm (19), 2 ♂♂, 9. and 11.viii.1985, INS 30552 and 30652. Levyj Ptys (48), 1 ♂, 22.vii.1983, INS 30453. Resava (61), 1 ♂, 22.vii.1988, INS 30248. Saken (64), 3 ♂♂, 8.vii.1983, INS 30451, 30551 and 30650. Saken – Narzan (65), 2

♂♂, 9. and 12.vii.1983, INS 30359 and 30755. Serbista (67), 1 ♂, 2.viii.1985, INS 30454. Zemo – Azara (77), 6 ♂♂, 10., 14. and 15.vii.1983, INS 30360, 30653, 30655, 30753, 30754 and 30756. Distribution: Species known from Iran, Armenia, Azerbaijan, Georgia and Russia (Wagner & Joost, 1983; Ježek et al., 2018, 2021a). New for Abkhazia.

Saraiella rotunda (Krek, 1970) – Unpublished records: Abkhazia: Azgara (9), 1 ♂, 16.vii.1983, INS 30757. Azgara – Narzan (10), 2 ♂♂, 1.viii.1985, INS 30656 and 30657. Distribution: European species, penetrates into Azerbaijan and Georgia; for information in detail, see Krek (1999) and Ježek et al. (2021a, b). New for Abkhazia.

Szaboiella hibernica (Tonnoir, 1940) – Published record: Ježek (2004a): Kot – Kot (43). Unpublished records: Abkhazia: Baskacara (11), 2 ♂♂, 18.vii.1983, INS 30429 and 30727. Below Adanga Pass (12), 1 ♂, 4.viii.1985, INS 30728. Dvurecje near Dou (28), 1 ♂, 21.vii.1988, INS 30331. Kot – Kot near Cimuri (44), 3 ♂♂, 11.viii.1985, INS 30428, 30529 and 30620. Distribution: European species, penetrates into Transcaucasia (Abkhazia), for details, see Ježek et al. (2021b).

Thornburghiella montana Ježek, Oboňa & Manko, 2021 – Unpublished records: Abkhazia: Baskacara (11), 1 ♂, 17.vii.1983, INS 30806. Saken – Narzan (65), 1 ♂, 12.vii.1983, INS 30534. Georgia: Svanetia (69), 3 ♂♂, 5.vii.2013, Chvojka leg., SW, INS 30803, 30804 and 30805. Distribution: Transcaucasian species known only from the original description from Georgia (Ježek et al., 2021c). New for Abkhazia.

Tonnoiriella arcuata Ježek, 1997 – Published record: Ježek (1997): Pskhu (58). Unpublished records: Georgia: Adjaria (6), 4 ♂♂, 30.vi. and 1.vii.2013, Chvojka leg., SW, INS 30684, 30778, 30779 and 30780. Svanetia (69), 1 ♂, 5.vii.2013, Chvojka leg., SW, INS 30388. Abkhazia: Azgara (9), 1 ♂, 16.vii.1983, INS 30683. Azgara – Narzan (10), 3 ♂♂, 1.viii.1985, INS 30577, 30578 and 30688. Baskacara (11), 1 ♂, 18.vii.1983, INS 30681. Below Adanga Pass (12), 4 ♂♂, 3. and 4.viii.1985, INS 30385, 30386, 30490 and 30686. Below Maruch Pass (14), 1 ♂, 17.vii.1983, INS 30393. Bzyb (17), 2 ♂♂, 5.viii.1985, INS 30379 and 30390. Cimuri (20), 2 ♂♂, 10. and 13.viii.1985, INS 30384 and 30493. Clou (23), 1 ♂, 8.viii.1988, INS 30285. Dou Pass (26), 1 ♂, 21.vii.1988, INS 30283. Dvurecje near Dou (28), 2 ♂♂, 20.vii.1988, INS 30091 and 30093. Gencvici (32), 1 ♂, 7.vii.1983, INS 30680. Kelasuri (40), 1 ♂,

25.viii.1985, INS 30391. Levyj Ptys (48), 4 ♂♂, 22.vii.1983, INS 30377, 30382, 30392 and 30492. Mercheuli (51), 2 ♂♂, 5.vii.1983, INS 30576 and 30579. Novyj Afon near Anuchva (54), 1 ♂, 19.viii.1985, INS 29088. Pskhu (58), 2 ♂♂, 25. and 27.vii.1988, INS 29089 and 30284. Pskhu near Dou (59), 3 ♂♂, 25.vii.1988, INS 29086, 29087 and 30288. Resava (61), 1 ♂, 22.vii.1988, INS 30184. Saken (64), 3 ♂♂, 8.vii.1983, INS 30380, 30491 and 30575. Saken – Narzan (65), 8 ♂♂, 9. and 12.vii.1983, INS 30282, 30286, 30289, 30387, 30494, 30574, 30580 and 30682. Serbista (67), 1 ♂, 2.viii.1985, INS 30389. Ubus (73), 2 ♂♂, 7.viii.1985, INS 30378 and 30687. Zemo – Azara (77), 7 ♂♂, 10., 14. and 15.vii.1983, INS 30287, 30381, 30383, 30581, 30685, 30689 and 30777. Distribution: This species was known so far only by its original description (Ježek, 1997) from Abkhazia. Now known from Georgia and Azerbaijan, as well (Oboňa et al., 2019; Ježek et al., 2021a).

Ulomyia cognata (Eaton, 1893) – Unpublished records: Georgia: Adjaria (6), 1 ♂, 30.vi.2013, Chvojka leg., SW, INS 30709. Abkhazia: Adanga Pass (5), 1 ♂, 4.viii.1985, INS 30014. Azgara – Narzan (10), 1 ♂, 1.viii.1985, INS 30012. Baskacara (11), 1 ♂, 18.vii.1983, INS 30313. Bzyb (17), 2 ♂♂, 5.viii.1985, INS 30013 and 30410. Kot – Kot (43), 1 ♂, 11.viii.1985, INS 30414. Ubus (73), 1 ♂, 7.viii.1985, INS 30011. Distribution: European species (Wagner 1990, 2019), known also from Armenia and Georgia (Ježek et al., 2018, 2021a). New for Abkhazia.

Summary of the results and conclusion

Psychodids fauna, mainly from Abkhazia and rarely from adjacent countries, such as Armenia, Georgia and Russia, is presented. Altogether 65 species were found from 33 genera. The most species-rich localities include the following: site 65 – Saken – Narzan (26 species), 58 – Pskhu (22 spp.), 77 – Zemo – Azara (20 spp.), and these localities, with a large diversity of plants and interesting different landscape morphology, were the mostly frequently sampled. On the other hand, the localities with the lowest species diversity (usually with a minimum diversity of plants and almost dried former wet habitats) were sites with just one species (localities 13 – Below Chimsa Pass, 15 – Below Ulm Pass, 24 – Cerna Voda, 34 – Ilori) and with two species (sites 1 – Achalsopeli, 3 – Achalseni near Sroma, 7 – Anaria, 30 – Gagra). The

Moth flies of Abkhazia with some additional faunistic data from Armenia, Georgia, and Russia

Table 1. List of localities with recorded species.

1	Achalsopeli (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica, auriculata</i>
2	Achalseni (Abkhazia)	<i>achalshenica, ckvitariorum, gemina, nubila, trinodulosa</i>
3	Achalseni near Sroma (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica, blandula</i>
4	Acigvara (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica, nubila, trinodulosa</i>
5	Adanga Pass (Abkhazia)	<i>cognata, phalaenoides, schumpkanica</i>
6	Adjaria (Georgia)	<i>ambigua, arcuata, balkanealpinus, balkanicum, blandula, caucasica (S.), cognata, furva, grusinicus, minuta, m. motasi, nubila, pseudexquisita, satchelli, silesiensis</i>
7	Anaria (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica, nubila</i>
8	Areni (Armenia)	<i>albipennis, alternata, bunae, lativentris, pannonica, pilularia, satchelli, ustulata</i>
9	Azgara (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica, arcuata, balkanealpinus, caucasica (S.), furva, grusinicus, lobata, nubila, ressl, rotunda, setigera, vaillanti</i>
10	Azgara – Narzan (Abkhazia)	<i>alternata, arcuata, balkanealpinus, blandula, buxtoni, caucasica (S.), cognata, furva, grusinicus, lobata, nubila, polyascoidea, ressl, rotunda, satchelli, trinodulosa</i>
11	Baskacara (Abkhazia)	<i>albipennis, alticola, arcuata, balkanealpinus, clouense, cognata, furva, gemina, grusinicus, hibernica, lobata, minuta, montana, petrosus, phalaenoides, pseudexquisita, ressl, schumpkanica, setigera, svanetica</i>
12	Below Adanga Pass (Abkhazia)	<i>albipennis, alticola, arcuata, balkanealpinus, grisescens, hibernica, nubila, petrosus, phalaenoides, ressl, satchelli</i>
13	Below Chimsa Pass (Abkhazia)	<i>schumpkanica</i>
14	Below Maruch Pass (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica, albipennis, arcuata, balkanealpinus, gemina, lobata, phalaenoides, pilularia, satchelli, svanetica, trinodulosa, zetterstedti</i>
15	Below Ulm Pass (Abkhazia)	<i>schumpkanica</i>
16	Beslachuba (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica, erminea, nubila</i>
17	Bzyb (Abkhazia)	<i>arcuata, balkanealpinus, cognata, compta, g. gracilis, lobata, nubila, palustris, phalaenoides</i>
18	Cebelda (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica, alternata, gemina, nubila, trinodulosa</i>
19	Chimsa near Ulm (Abkhazia)	<i>ressl, schumpkanica</i>
20	Cimuri (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica, albipennis, alternata, arcuata, balkanealpinus, blandula, buxtoni, cinerea, gemina, g. gracilis, minuta, nubila</i>
21	Cimuri near Achalseni (Abkhazia)	<i>g. gracilis, inopinata</i>
22	Cchalta (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica, auriculata, gemina, grusinicus, nubila, polyascoidea, pseudexquisita</i>
23	Clou (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica, arcuata, balkanealpinus, blandula, caucasica (S.), ckvitariorum, clouense, erminea, fallax, grusinicus, nubila, phalaenoides, trinodulosa</i>
24	Cerna Voda (Abkhazia)	<i>balkanealpinus</i>
25	Dagomys (Russia)	<i>cinerea</i>
26	Dou Pass (Abkhazia)	<i>albipennis, arcuata, phalaenoides</i>
27	Dou near Bzyb (Abkhazia)	<i>caucasica (S.)</i>
28	Dvurecje near Dou (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica, arcuata, balkanealpinus, caucasica (S.), furva, grusinicus, hibernica, lobata, nubila, satchelli</i>
29	Dzgerda (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica, buxtoni, nubila</i>

Table 1 continued...

30	Gagra (Abkhazia)	<i>grusanicus, nubila</i>
31	Gali (Abkhazia)	<i>alternata, polyascoidea, trinodulosa</i>
32	Gencvici (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica, arcuata, blandula, caucasica (B.), furva, gemina, grusanicus, nubila, polyascoidea, trinodulosa</i>
33	GES – Sukhumi (Abkhazia)	<i>blandula, cinerea, ckvitariorum</i>
34	Ilori (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica</i>
35	Imereli (Georgia)	<i>nubila</i>
36	Juznyj Prijut Pass (Abkhazia)	<i>caucasica (S.), gemina, schumpkanica, svanetica</i>
37	Kaldachvara (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica, afonensis, blandula, cinerea, nubila</i>
38	Kaldachvara near Mjusoera (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica, auriculata</i>
39	Kaman (Abkhazia)	<i>blandula, cinerea, ckvitariorum, exquisita, gemina, griseus, hirtella, inopinata, nubila, phalaenoides, trinodulosa</i>
40	Kelasuri (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica, arcuata, blandula, caucasica (S.), ckvitariorum, clouense, erminea, exquisita, griseus, grusanicus, lobata, phalaenoides, trinodulosa</i>
41	Kingdi (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica, auriculata, nubila</i>
42	Kochora (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica</i>
43	Kot – Kot (Abkhazia)	<i>cognata, hibernica, lobata, petrosus</i>
44	Kot – Kot near Cimuri (Abkhazia)	<i>balkanealpinus, gemina, griseus, hibernica, lobata, minuta, nubila, petrosus</i>
45	Kot – Kot near Ulm Pass (Abkhazia)	<i>lobata, nubila, petrosus, setigera</i>
46	Kutol (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica, auriculata, nubila, polyascoidea</i>
47	Lehvaz (Armenia)	<i>blandula, bunae, ustulata</i>
48	Levyj Ptsy (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica, alticola, arcuata, balkanealpinus, blandula, buxtoni, caucasica (S.), furva, gemina, g. gracilis, grusanicus, nubila, polyascoidea, pseudexquisita, resli</i>
49	Macara (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica, achalshenica, afonensis, alternata, ckvitariorum, exquisita, grusanicus, nubila</i>
50	Maruch near Adanga (Abkhazia)	<i>balkanealpinus</i>
51	Mercheuli (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica, achalshenica, alternata, arcuata, blandula, caucasica (S.), ckvitariorum, erminea, exquisita, georgica, grusanicus, inopinata, minuta, negrobovi, nubila, phalaenoides, trinodulosa</i>
52	Mramba (Abkhazia)	<i>alternata, cinerea, gemina, inopinata, nubila, phalaenoides, trinodulosa</i>
53	Niznaja Zemo – Azara (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica, caucasica (S.), gemina, grusanicus, nubila, polyascoidea, trinodulosa</i>
54	Novyj Afon near Anuchva (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica, achalshenica, afonensis, arcuata, blandula, cinerea, ckvitariorum, erminea, furva, inopinata, polyascoidea, trinodulosa</i>
55	Ocamcira (Abkhazia)	<i>alternata, auriculata, nubila, uniformata, ustulata</i>
56	Okumi (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica, alternata, auriculata, exquisita, nubila, trinodulosa</i>
57	Otap (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica, afonensis, auriculata, balkanealpinus, blandula, ckvitariorum, grusanicus, nubila</i>
58	Pskhu (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica, afonensis, alternata, arcuata, balkanealpinus, blandula, buxtoni, caucasica (S.), cinerea, erminea, furva, gemina, georgica, g. gracilis, grusanicus, manicata, negrobovi, nubila, palustris, polyascoidea, pskhuensis, trinodulosa</i>

Table 1 continued...

59	Pskhu near Dou (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica</i> , <i>arcuata</i> , <i>balkanealpinus</i> , <i>erminea</i> , <i>g. gracilis</i> , <i>grusinicus</i> , <i>nubila</i> , <i>palustris</i> , <i>polyascoidea</i> , <i>trinodulosa</i> , <i>uniformata</i>
60	Reka near Gali (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica</i> , <i>alternata</i> , <i>trinodulosa</i>
61	Resava (Abkhazia)	<i>arcuata</i> , <i>balkanealpinus</i> , <i>caucasica</i> (S.), <i>ressli</i>
62	Rica (Abkhazia)	<i>albipennis</i> , <i>balkanealpinus</i> , <i>balkanicum</i> , <i>gemina</i> , <i>lobata</i> , <i>negrobovi</i>
63	Sagra near Tamys (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica</i> , <i>brevicornis</i> , <i>trinodulosa</i>
64	Saken (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica</i> , <i>arcuata</i> , <i>balkanealpinus</i> , <i>furva</i> , <i>gemina</i> , <i>grusinicus</i> , <i>nubila</i> , <i>polyascoidea</i> , <i>ressli</i> , <i>trinodulosa</i>
65	Saken – Narzan (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica</i> , <i>albipennis</i> , <i>arcuata</i> , <i>balkanealpinus</i> , <i>blandula</i> , <i>brevicornis</i> , <i>buxtoni</i> , <i>carthusiana</i> , <i>caucasica</i> (B.), <i>caucasica</i> (S.), <i>cinerea</i> , <i>crassipennis</i> , <i>furva</i> , <i>gemina</i> , <i>grisescens</i> , <i>lobata</i> , <i>montana</i> , <i>nubila</i> , <i>phalaenoides</i> , <i>polyascoidea</i> , <i>ressli</i> , <i>satchelli</i> , <i>schumpkanica</i> , <i>setigera</i> , <i>svanetica</i> , <i>trinodulosa</i>
66	Saken near Juznyj Prijut Pass (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica</i> , <i>furva</i> , <i>nubila</i> , <i>polyascoidea</i>
67	Serbista (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica</i> , <i>alticola</i> , <i>arcuata</i> , <i>balkanealpinus</i> , <i>caucasica</i> (S.), <i>crassipennis</i> , <i>gemina</i> , <i>lobata</i> , <i>petrosus</i> , <i>phalaenoides</i> , <i>ressli</i> , <i>satchelli</i> , <i>setigera</i> , <i>trinodulosa</i> , <i>zetterstedti</i>
68	Shvanidzor (Armenia)	<i>achalshenica</i> , <i>alternata</i> , <i>ustulata</i>
69	Svanetia (Georgia)	<i>arcuata</i> , <i>blandula</i> , <i>grusinicus</i> , <i>montana</i> , <i>m. motasi</i> , <i>phalaenoides</i> , <i>schumpkanica</i>
70	Sroma (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica</i> , <i>nubila</i> , <i>polyascoidea</i>
71	Tamys (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica</i> , <i>alternata</i> , <i>brevicornis</i> , <i>minuta</i> , <i>nubila</i> , <i>uniformata</i>
72	Tkvarceli (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica</i> , <i>balkanealpinus</i> , <i>blandula</i> , <i>ckvitariorum</i> , <i>nubila</i> , <i>trivialis</i>
73	Ubus (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica</i> , <i>albipennis</i> , <i>alticola</i> , <i>arcuata</i> , <i>balkanealpinus</i> , <i>caucasica</i> (B.), <i>cognata</i> , <i>grisescens</i> , <i>lobata</i> , <i>petrosus</i> , <i>phalaenoides</i> , <i>schumpkanica</i> , <i>setigera</i>
74	Ubus near Bzyb (Abkhazia)	<i>schumpkanica</i>
75	Vedi (Armenia)	<i>achalshenica</i>
76	Yerevan (Armenia)	<i>albipennis</i> , <i>alternata</i> , <i>ustulata</i>
77	Zemo – Azara (Abkhazia)	<i>abchazica</i> , <i>achalshenica</i> , <i>arcuata</i> , <i>balkanealpinus</i> , <i>blandula</i> , <i>caucasica</i> (B.), <i>caucasica</i> (S.), <i>erminea</i> , <i>furva</i> , <i>g. gracilis</i> , <i>grusinicus</i> , <i>inopinata</i> , <i>m. motasi</i> , <i>nubila</i> , <i>phalaenoides</i> , <i>polyascoidea</i> , <i>pseudexquisita</i> , <i>ressli</i> , <i>schumpkanica</i> , <i>trinodulosa</i>

most common species in this study include *Parajungiella abchazica* Ježek, 1985 (41 sites), *Pneumia nubila* (Meigen, 1818) (36), *Tonnoiriella arcuata* Ježek, 1997 (24), and *Threticus balkanealpinus* Krek, 1972 (22). Some species are known so far, unfortunately, from only the holotype locality – one specimen (*Kvazbamormia pskhuensis* Ježek, 1995) in contrast to species with a generally large distribution and registered here infrequently by accident: e.g. *Seoda carthusiana* (Vaillant, 1972), *Pneumia compta* (Eaton, 1893), *Pericoma (Pachypericoma) fallax* Eaton, 1893, *Trichopsychoda hirtella* (Tonnoir, 1919), *Berdeniella manicata*

(Tonnoir, 1920), *Pneumia trivialis* (Eaton, 1893) and *Psychomormia vaillanti* (Wagner, 1977).

New records for Abkhazia (31 species) were ascertained: *Logima albipennis* (Zetterstedt, 1850), *Tinearia alternata* (Say, 1824), *Psychoda alticola* Vaillant, 1973, *Coprotopsychoa brevicornis* (Tonnoir, 1940), *Chodopsycha buxtoni* (Withers, 1988), *Seoda carthusiana* (Vaillant, 1972), *Berdeniella caucasica* Wagner, 1981, *Ulomyia cognata* (Eaton, 1893), *Pneumia compta* (Eaton, 1893), *Psychoda crassipennis* Tonnoir, 1940, *Pericoma (Pericoma) exquisita* Eaton, 1893, *Psychoa grisescens* (Tonnoir, 1922), *Clytocerus (Boreoclytocerus) grusinicus* Wagner,

1981, *Trichopsychoda hirtella* (Tonnoir, 1919), *Pericoma* (*Pericoma*) *inopinata* Ježek, Oboňa & Manko, 2021, *Berdeniella manicata* (Tonnoir, 1920), *Thornburghiella montana* Ježek, Oboňa & Manko, 2021, *Pericoma* (*Pericoma*) *m. motasi* Vaillant, 1978, *Psychoda phalaenoides* (Linnaeus, 1758), *Pneumia pilularia* (Tonnoir, 1940), *Pericoma* (*Pericoma*) *pseudexquisita* Tonnoir, 1940, *Saraiella ressli* Wagner, 1981, *Saraiella rotunda* (Krek, 1970), *Logima satchelli* (Quate, 1955), *Berdeniella schumpkanica* Vaillant & Joost, 1983, *Ypsydocha setigera* (Tonnoir, 1922), *Psychomora trinodulosa* (Tonnoir, 1922), *Pneumia trivialis* (Eaton, 1893), *Psychoda uniformata* Haseman, 1907, *Paramormia* (*Duckhousiella*) *ustulata* (Walker, 1856), *Psychomormia vaillanti* (Wagner, 1977) and *Logima zetterstedti* Ježek, 1983.

Several species from neighbouring countries were identified in this paper, e.g. *Tonnoiriella arcuata* Ježek, 1997, *Clytocerus* (*Boreoclytocerus*) *grusinicus* Wagner, 1981, *Threticus balkanealpinus* Krek, 1972, *Thornburghiella montana* Ježek, Oboňa & Manko, 2021, *Pericoma* (*Pericoma*) *motasi motasi* Vaillant, 1978, *Pneumia nubila* (Meigen, 1818), *Psychoda phalaenoides* (Linnaeus, 1758) and *Pericoma* (*Pericoma*) *pseudexquisita* Tonnoir, 1940, however, all mentioned species were published already from Georgia (Wagner 1981, Oboňa et al., 2019 and Ježek et al., 2021c), from territory other than Abkhazia. For all that, *Seoda ambigua* (Eaton, 1893), *Philosepedon* (*Trichosepedon*) *balkanicum* Krek, 1971, *Yomormia furva* (Tonnoir, 1940), *Psychodula minuta* (Banks, 1894), *Berdeniella schumpkanica* (Vaillant & Joost, 1983) and *Promormia silesiensis* Ježek, 1983, are new for Georgia.

Logima albipennis (Zetterstedt, 1850), *Tinearia alternata* (Say, 1824), *Paramormia* (*Duckhousiella*) *ustulata* (Walker, 1856) and *Pneumia pilularia* (Tonnoir, 1940) were published from Armenia (Ježek et al., 2018), however, *Yomormia achalshenica* Ježek, 1987, *Pericoma* (*Pericoma*) *bunae* Krek, 1979, *Tinearia lativentris* (Berdén, 1952) and *Pericoma* (*Pericoma*) *pannonica* Szabó, 1960, are new for Armenia.

Pericoma (*Pachypericoma*) *blandula* Eaton, 1893, was registered from Georgia and Armenia (Ježek et al., 2018, 2021a), nevertheless, *Logima satchelli* (Quate, 1955) represents a new record for both Georgia and Armenia.

Psychodocha cinerea (Banks, 1894) was published from Russia (Siberia – Ježek, 1992b) and *Berdeniella*

schumpkanica Vaillant & Joost, 1983, is also known from Russia (see Vaillant & Joost, 1983: Terskol + stream Schumka).

The Caucasus region (Armenia, Azerbaijan, and Georgia) is considered to be the most biologically rich and most endangered region in the world, a so-called “Biodiversity hotspot” with an exceptional richness of endemic and endangered species (Myers et al., 2000; Krever et al., 2001; Williams et al., 2011; Mumladze et al., 2020). But there was only scarce information about the Psychodidae family from here. As there are also many, extremely rare species in this family in the Caucasus (probably Caucasus or highland endemics) (e.g. *Sycorax caucasica*, *Kvazbamormia pskhuensis*, *Lepimormia georgica*, *Mormia ckvitariorum*, *Yomormia achalshenica*, *Yomormia afonensis*, *Parajungiella abchazica*, *Seoda svanetica*, *Philosepedon* (*Trichosepedon*) *clouense*, *Threticus petrosus*, *Berdeniella caucasica*, *Berdeniella schumpkanica*, *Clytocerus* (*Boreoclytocerus*) *grusinicus*, *Pericoma* (*Pericoma*) *inopinata*, *Saraiella ressli*, *Thornburghiella montana*), it is appropriate to perceive this area as being the most biologically rich and most endangered region in the world also in terms of biodiversity of the Psychodidae family. However, it needs to be given increased attention not only for these rare species, but, for example, from the point of view of island ecology or biodiversity protection.

Research in this area can also contribute to understanding the spread of different species and may contribute to the understanding of the factors that limit this spread.

Knowledge about the biodiversity of the Caucasus is crucial for the protection not only of local nature, but also insects, especially Diptera; extremely “unaesthetic” epidemiological/economic groups are unimportant and given only marginal attention. Also, the ecological significance of insects is often overlooked. Their main ecological functions and ecosystem services in ecosystems include nutrient recycling, pollination, predation/parasitism and decomposition of biological material (Samways, 1993; Kim, 1993; Naeem et al., 2021).

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Checklist of species of the family Psychodidae from selected areas of Transcaucasia

Species new for country are marked with an asterisk (*). Abbreviations: Arm – Armenia, Aze – Azerbaijan, Geo – Georgia, (Abk) – Abkhazia (see in Ježek et al., 2018, 2021 and Oboňa et al., 2019).

Subfamily Phlebotominae

<i>Phlebotomus (Adlerius) balcanicus</i> Theodor, 1958	Aze, Geo
<i>Phlebotomus (Adlerius) brevis</i> Theodor et Mesghali, 1964	Aze, Geo
<i>Phlebotomus (Adlerius) chinensis tauriae</i> Perfiliew, 1966	Geo
<i>Phlebotomus (Adlerius) halepensis</i> Theodor, 1958	Arm, Aze, Geo
<i>Phlebotomus (Adlerius) longiductus</i> Parrot, 1928	Geo
<i>Phlebotomus (Adlerius) simici</i> Nitzulescu, 1931	Arm, Aze, Geo
<i>Phlebotomus (Larroussius) kandelaki</i> Shurenkova, 1929	Arm, Aze, Geo
<i>Phlebotomus (Larroussius) major syriacus</i> Adler et Theodor, 1931	Arm, Aze, Geo
<i>Phlebotomus (Larroussius) perfiliewi perfiliewi</i> Parrot, 1930	Geo
<i>Phlebotomus (Larroussius) perfiliewi transcaucasicus</i> Perfiliew, 1937	Aze, Geo
<i>Phlebotomus (Larroussius) perniciosus</i> Newstead, 1911	Aze
<i>Phlebotomus (Larroussius) tobbi</i> Adler et Theodor in Adler, Theodor et Lourie, 1930	Arm, Aze, Geo
<i>Phlebotomus (Larroussius) wenyoni</i> Adler et Theodor in Adler, Theodor et Lourie, 1930	Geo
<i>Phlebotomus (Paraphlebotomus) alexandri</i> Sinton, 1928	Arm Aze, Geo
<i>Phlebotomus (Paraphlebotomus) caucasicus</i> Marzinovsky, 1917	Arm, Aze, Geo
<i>Phlebotomus (Paraphlebotomus) jacusieli</i> Theodor, 1947	Aze, Geo
<i>Phlebotomus (Paraphlebotomus) mongolensis</i> Sinton, 1928	Aze, Geo
<i>Phlebotomus (Paraphlebotomus) sergenti</i> Parrot, 1917	Arm, Aze, Geo
<i>Phlebotomus (Paraphlebotomus) similis</i> Perfiliew, 1963 sensu Artemiev et Neronov, 1984	Arm, Aze, Geo
<i>Phlebotomus (Phlebotomus) papatasi</i> (Scopoli, 1786)	Arm, Aze, Geo
<i>Sergentomyia (Neophlebotomus) pawlowskyi</i> (Perfiliew, 1933)	Arm, Aze, Geo
<i>Sergentomyia (Parrotomyia) palestinensis</i> (Adler et Theodor, 1927)	Arm, Aze, Geo
<i>Sergentomyia (Sergentomyia) dentata</i> (Sinton, 1933)	Aze, Geo

Subfamily Sycoracinae

<i>Sycorax caucasica</i> Ježek, 1990	Geo (Abk)
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Subfamily Trichomyiinae

<i>Trichomyia urbica</i> Haliday in Curtis, 1839	Aze
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Subfamily Psychodinae

<i>Apsycha pusilla</i> (Tonnoir, 1922)	Aze
<i>Bazarella centiretinacula</i> Wagner, 1981	Geo
<i>Berdeniella manicata</i> (Tonnoir, 1920)	Geo (Abk*)
<i>Berdeniella caucasica</i> Wagner, 1981	Geo (Abk*)
<i>Berdeniella schumpkanica</i> Vaillant & Joost, 1983	Geo* (Abk*)
<i>Coprotychoda brevicornis</i> (Tonnoir, 1940)	Geo (Abk*)
<i>Feuerborniella obscura</i> (Tonnoir, 1919)	Geo
<i>Chodopsycha lobata</i> (Tonnoir, 1940)	Geo (Abk)
<i>Chodopsycha buxtoni</i> (Withers, 1988)	Geo (Abk*)
<i>Clogmia albipunctata</i> (Williston, 1893)	Arm, Aze, Geo
<i>Clytocerus (Boreoclytocerus) grusinicus</i> Wagner, 1981	Aze, Geo (Abk*)
<i>Joostiella caucasica</i> Vaillant, 1983	Arm
<i>Kvazbamormia pskhuensis</i> Ježek, 1994	Geo (Abk)
<i>Lepimormia georgica</i> (Wagner, 1981)	Geo (Abk)

<i>Logima albipennis</i> (Zetterstedt, 1850)	Arm, Aze, Geo (Abk*)
<i>Logima erminea</i> (Eaton, 1893)	Geo (Abk)
<i>Logima satchelli</i> (Quate, 1955)	Arm*, Aze, Geo* (Abk*)
<i>Logima sigma</i> (Kincaid, 1899)	Aze
<i>Logima zetterstedti</i> Ježek, 1983	Geo (Abk*)
<i>Mormia ckvitariorum</i> Ježek, 1987	Aze, Geo (Abk)
<i>Mormia malickyi</i> Vaillant, 1974	Geo
<i>Parajungiella abchazica</i> Ježek, 1985	Arm, Geo (Abk)
<i>Parajungiella serbica</i> (Krek, 1985)	Aze
<i>Parajungiella monikae</i> (Wagner & Joost, 1986)	Arm
<i>Panimerus denticulatus</i> Krek, 1971	Aze, Geo
<i>Paramormia (Duckhousiella) ustulata</i> (Walker, 1856)	Arm, Aze, Geo (Abk*)
<i>Paramormia (Paramormia) fratercula</i> (Eaton, 1893)	Arm
<i>Paramormia (Paramormia) polyascoidea</i> (Krek, 1971)	Arm, Geo (Abk)
<i>Parabazarella joosti laleharica</i> Ježek, 1990	Geo
<i>Pericoma (Pachypericoma) blandula</i> Eaton, 1893	Arm, Aze, Geo (Abk)
<i>Pericoma (Pachypericoma) fallax</i> Eaton, 1893	Aze, Geo (Abk)
<i>Pericoma (Pachypericoma) nielseni</i> Kvifte, 2010	Aze, Geo
<i>Pericoma (Pericoma) bosniaca</i> Krek, 1966	Arm, Aze, Geo
<i>Pericoma (Pericoma) bunae</i> Krek, 1979	Arm*, Aze
<i>Pericoma (Pericoma) exquisita</i> Eaton, 1893	Arm, Aze, Geo (Abk*)
<i>Pericoma inopinata</i> Ježek, Oboňa & Manko 2021	Aze, Geo (Abk*)
<i>Pericoma (Pericoma) kariana</i> Vaillant, 1978	Aze
<i>Pericoma (Pericoma) motasi motasi</i> Vaillant, 1978	Aze, Geo (Abk*)
<i>Pericoma (Pericoma) pannonica</i> Szabó, 1960	Arm*
<i>Pericoma (Pericoma) pseudexquisita</i> Tonnoir, 1940	Geo (Abk*)
<i>Pericoma platystyla</i> Wagner, 1986	Arm
<i>Peripsychoda auriculata</i> (Haliday in Curtis, 1839)	Arm, Geo (Abk)
? <i>Philosepedon (Philosepedon) wagneri</i> Omelková et Ježek, 2012	? Geo (see Note in Oboňa et al., 2021b)
? <i>Philosepedon (Trichosepedon) atschitaricum</i> Vaillant et Joost, 1983	? Geo (see Note in Oboňa et al., 2021b)
<i>Philosepedon (Trichosepedon) balkanicum</i> Krek, 1971	Geo* (Abk)
<i>Philosepedon (Trichosepedon) clouense</i> Ježek, 1994	Geo (Abk)
<i>Pneumia canescens</i> (Meigen, 1804)	Arm, Aze
<i>Pneumia compta</i> (Eaton, 1893)	Geo (Abk*)
<i>Pneumia fuehzulii</i> Ježek, Oboňa & Manko 2022	Aze
<i>Pneumia gracilis gracilis</i> (Eaton, 1893)	Aze, Geo
<i>Pneumia gracilis kandavanica</i> (Ježek 1990)	Aze
<i>Pneumia nubila</i> (Meigen, 1818)	Arm, Aze, Geo (Abk)
<i>Pneumia joosti</i> (Wagner, 1981)	Arm
<i>Pneumia palustris</i> (Meigen, 1804)	Geo
<i>Pneumia pilularia</i> (Tonnoir, 1940)	Arm, Aze, Geo (Abk*)
<i>Pneumia trivialis</i> (Eaton, 1893)	Aze, Geo (Abk*)
<i>Promormia silesiensis</i> (Ježek, 1983)	Aze, Geo*
<i>Psycha grisescens</i> (Tonnoir, 1922)	Aze, Geo (Abk*)
<i>Psychoda alticola</i> Vaillant, 1973	Geo (Abk*)
<i>Psychoda crassipennis</i> Tonnoir, 1940	Geo (Abk*)
<i>Psychoda phalaenoides</i> (Linné, 1758)	Aze, Geo (Abk*)
<i>Psychoda uniformata</i> Haseman, 1907	Arm, Aze, Geo (Abk*)
<i>Psychodocha cinerea</i> (Banks, 1894)	Arm, Aze, Geo (Abk)
<i>Psychodocha gemina</i> (Eaton, 1904)	Aze, Geo (Abk)
<i>Psychodula minuta</i> (Banks, 1894)	Geo* (Abk)
<i>Psychomora mycophila</i> (Vaillant, 1988)	Aze
<i>Psychomora trinodulosa</i> (Tonnoir, 1922)	Aze, Geo (Abk*)
<i>Psychomormia vaillanti</i> (Wagner, 1977)	Geo (Abk*)

Jan Ježek, Jozef Oboňa, Peter Manko

<i>Saraiella ressl</i> Wagner, 1981	Arm, Aze, Geo (Abk*)
<i>Saraiella rotunda</i> (Krek, 1970)	Aze, Geo (Abk*)
<i>Seoda ambigua</i> (Eaton, 1893)	Geo*
<i>Seoda carthusiana</i> (Vaillant, 1972)	Geo (Abk*)
<i>Seoda svanetica</i> (Ježek, 1989)	Geo (Abk)
<i>Szaboiella hibernica</i> (Tonnoir, 1940)	Geo (Abk)
<i>Thornburghiella montana</i> Ježek, Oboňa & Manko 2021	Geo (Abk*)
<i>Thornburghiella veve</i> Oboňa & Ježek, 2017	Arm, Aze
<i>Thornburghiella salih</i> Ježek, Oboňa & Manko 2022	Aze, Geo
<i>Threticus balkanealpinus</i> Krek, 1972	Geo (Abk)
<i>Threticus negrobovi</i> Vaillant, 1972	Geo (Abk)
<i>Threticus petrosus</i> Ježek, 1997	Geo (Abk)
<i>Trichopsychoda hirtella</i> (Tonnoir, 1919)	Geo (Abk*)
<i>Tinearia alternata</i> (Say, 1824)	Arm, Aze, Geo (Abk*)
<i>Tinearia lativentris</i> (Berdén, 1952)	Arm*
<i>Tonnoiriella arcuata</i> Ježek, 1997	Aze, Geo
<i>Ulomyia cognata</i> (Eaton, 1893)	Arm, Geo (Abk*)
<i>Yomormia petrovi</i> Ježek, 1985	Arm
<i>Yomormia achalshenica</i> Ježek, 1987	Arm*, Geo (Abk)
<i>Yomormia afonensis</i> Ježek, 1987	Aze, Geo (Abk)
<i>Yomormia furva</i> (Tonnoir, 1940)	Geo* (Abk)
<i>Ypsydocha setigera</i> (Tonnoir, 1922)	Geo (Abk*)

Summary: Arm (36 + 5*), Aze (61), Geo (88 + 7*) (Abk) (26 + 31*).